

SVALBARD ENVIRONMENTAL
PROTECTION FUND

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Interdisciplinary archaeological fieldwork on Blomstrand, Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen

July 12 – 20, 2014

Final report

Non-technical summary

In July 2014, researchers carried out interdisciplinary fieldwork at the former British mining settlement and quarries on Blomstrand in Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen. They formulated two main questions: **1) why did past attempts to quarry marble on this Arctic island fail** and **2) what was the lasting impact of this industry on the local environment?** In order to generate answers, the archaeologist enlisted the help of a geologist, a biologist, and a team of divers. The geologist carried out a ground-penetrating-radar (GPR) survey to investigate the quality of the marble below the surface. The biologist conducted a vegetation survey to identify any foreign plants that the miners might have introduced and to look for signs that livestock known from old photographs might have fertilised the ground. The divers inspected the small natural harbour of Peirsonhamna to see if the industrial past had left any submerged traces. In addition to the fieldwork, the archaeologist undertook archival research in Great Britain in autumn 2014 to search for other real or potential reasons that could have caused the abandonment of the quarries.

The geologist was able to show that the marble was frequently fractured, but between fracture zones, there were also areas of rock that could have been worked successfully. The biologist identified newly appeared plants, especially grasses, which grew around some but not all of the former buildings in the settlement. Further analysis will have to show whether the animal (or human) dung had enriched the soil. The diving team found only a few large metal objects under water, which provided common algae with fixed hard surfaces on which to grow, but on the whole, the mining operations did not seem to have had any visible effect on Peirsonhamna.

While the GPR survey was inconclusive about the reasons for the site's abandonment, the historical documents consulted in British archives suggest some serious foul play by the company before and probably after the First World War. They also show that there was a growing demand for marble before the conflict. Afterwards, the market crashed because the British Government subsidised affordable housing for returning British soldiers instead of wasting limited resources on luxury building, i.e. the construction of villas, cinemas, theatres, and such like. It appears that the discontinuation of the marble quarries had little to do with the actual stone but was a logical decision in view of what was happening in Europe at the time.

Keywords

Archaeology, Blomstrand, development, diving, environmental impact, geology, GPR, historical ecology, history, industry, marble, metal detecting, mining, newly appearing plants, quarrying, Spitsbergen, Svalbard, vegetation

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Introduction

Interdisciplinary archaeological fieldwork took place on the Arctic island of Blomstrand in Kongsfjorden, Svalbard, Norway, approximately $78^{\circ}57'41''\text{N}$ and $12^{\circ}2'38''\text{E}$ (Fig. 1) between July 12 and 20, 2014.

Fig. 1 Location of the Arctic island of Blomstrand in Kongsfjorden, Svalbard, Norway. (Map: Norwegian Polar Institute)

It comprised a non-intrusive ground-penetrating radar (GPR) survey, a vegetation survey, and a reconnaissance dive in Peirsonhamna. These investigations were undertaken as part of two different research projects. The first was “Marble at Fault” (RiS ID 6912), which was funded by the Svalbard Environmental Protection Fund

(Svalbards Miljøvernfond) and supported by the University of Groningen (RUG). The second was “Environmental consequences of four hundred years of natural-resource exploitation on Spitsbergen” (“Consequences of exploitation” in short, RiS ID 6917), which was funded by the Netherlands Organisation of Scientific Research (NWO) and also supported by the RUG.

Throughout the fieldwork and on both projects, the archaeologist and author of this report Dr Frigga Kruse of the Arctic Centre of the RUG was the principal investigator. She is indebted to the geologist Dr Benjamin Koster of RWTH Aachen University, the biologist Dr Maarten Loonen of the Arctic Centre of the RUG as well as station leader of the Netherlands Arctic Station in Ny Ålesund, and the diving supervisor Mr Max Schwanitz and his team of divers of the Alfred-Wegener-Institut (AWI) for their invaluable scientific expertise and practical support in the field. The fieldwork also benefitted from the extensive logistical services offered by Kings Bay AS in Ny Ålesund. Furthermore, Kruse extends her thanks to the Georadar-Forum for critical methodological recommendations as well as the Svalbard Museum and *Svalbardposten* for providing an important platform for education and outreach.

Aims and objectives

The fieldwork being part of two different research projects, it combined the aims and objectives of both in equal measures.

The overall aim of “Marble at Fault” was of an industrial archaeological nature. The project aimed to disclose why historical attempts of large-scale quarrying of High Arctic marble failed on Marble Island (historically speaking). During the fieldwork, Kruse intended to test the hypothesis that structural geological changes had negatively affected the marble (Siggerud 1960) by engaging geological expertise to conduct a non-intrusive geophysical survey at carefully chosen locations on the island. More specifically, ground-penetrating radar (GPR) would be used to discern if there were structural weaknesses in the vicinity of known historical quarries and boreholes, which may be to blame for their abandonment. The title of the project “Marble at Fault” is a play on words as a certain type of structural weakness is known in geology as a fault. To prevent foregone conclusions, Kruse also carried out additional archival research in Great Britain after the fieldwork with the objective of identifying other reasons, real or potential, for the discontinuation of the quarries.

The overall aim of “Consequences of exploitation” was of rooted in historical ecology. The project aimed to qualify and quantify the anthropogenic impact of historical exploration and quarrying on the local terrestrial and coastal ecosystems of Marble Island. Hence, Loonen undertook a vegetation survey in order to identify non-indigenous plant species, specifically grasses, that may have been introduced as a result of the industrial operations. Secondly, Schwanitz and a team of divers carried out a series of dives in the natural harbour of Peirsonhamna in order to detect if the operations had any lasting effects under water.

Broadly speaking, the fieldwork would generate new knowledge about Svalbard’s industrial past and cultural heritage, thereby improving academic and public awareness of this historical mining site. Uncovering crucial information about the hither-to poorly understood and probably unique material remains of Arctic marble quarrying could potentially benefit the archipelago by enhancing their value as a source of historical and polar knowledge, as an intense visitor experience of a bygone industrial age, and as a source of revenue through improved tourism.

Geological, tectonic, and historical-archaeological setting

The focus of the interdisciplinary fieldwork lay on the south-western quarter of Blomstrand between Peirsonhamna on the south coast and Grottevika on the west coast (Fig. 2). As the historical British name of Marble Island suggests, an Englishman found it to consist of marble in 1906, and a range of material remains attesting to subsequent exploration and quarrying are well-preserved here. It is important, therefore, to gain an understanding of the underlying geology of those areas that merited further investigation as well as the historical-archaeological work done to date, in particular any questions left unanswered.

Blomstrandhalvøya, karst features

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--|
| Bedrock with no or thin cover | Moraine cover |
| Marble quarry, abandoned | Palaeokarst (Devonian and Carboniferous) |
| Mining site, abandoned | Fault in bedrock |

Karst features mapped by S.-E. Lauritzen, Univ. of Bergen, 2006; modified by W. Dallmann, 2011:

Names shown in light grey are not officially recognised.

- | | |
|---------------------|----------------------------|
| Marine cave, active | Escarpment of karst origin |
| Marine cave, relict | Spring |
| Karst cave, relict | Doline, sinkhole |

Fig. 2 The island of Blomstrand. The fieldwork focussed on the south-western quarter between Peirsonhamna to the south and Grottevika to the west. (Map: W. Dallmann.)

Geological and tectonic setting

Svalbard represents the emergent northwestern part of the Barents Shelf, which uplifted during the Late Mesozoic and Cenozoic (e.g. Johnson et al. 2001, Dallmann 2007). The uplift of the archipelago was most extensive in the northern and western parts, leaving gradually older rocks in those directions (Johnson et al. 2001). The geological record of Svalbard ranges from possible Archaean age to the recent past and shows a multi-orogenic development with prominent tectonic events at several ages (e.g. Dallmann 2007, Elvevold et al. 2007). The main geological record of Svalbard can be separated into three broad divisions: the basement of igneous and metamorphic rocks formed during Precambrian to Silurian times, which has suffered several episodes of folding and alteration; unaltered Late Palaeozoic to Cenozoic sedimentary rocks, which form a trough-shaped structure (Central Tertiary Spitsbergen Basin) from the Isfjorden area (central Spitsbergen) to the south; and unconsolidated Quaternary surficial deposits formed during and after the last ice age (e.g. Dallmann 2007, Elvevold et al. 2007).

A dominant NNW-SSE trending structural grain on Spitsbergen comprises several similarly aligned episodes of tectonic deformation (e.g. Johnson et al. 2001, Pirli et al. 2013). Svalbard's tectonic and geologic regions may be divided into: Precambrian to early Silurian rocks (Pre-Old Red basement) in the north-eastern part of Spitsbergen and on Nordaustlandet; Devonian cover rocks and grabens on northern Spitsbergen; the Central Tertiary Spitsbergen Basin; Triassic and partly Cretaceous platform areas on the eastern parts of Spitsbergen and on Barentsøya and Edgeøya; and the Tertiary fold-and-thrust belt along the west coast of Spitsbergen, which has possibly reactivated older structures (e.g. Johnson et al. 2001, Dallmann 2007, Elvevold et al. 2007).

The area under investigation in this study is located in the Kongsfjorden area (northwestern Spitsbergen), which is characterised by Mesoproterozoic rocks in the northern part, respectively Carboniferous and Permian as well as Palaeogene and Neogene rocks in the southern parts of the fjord. The NNW-SSE trending faults by the Tertiary fold-and-thrust belt dominate the younger tectonic regime in this area. Furthermore, deglaciation of the Kongfjord is reported since the Late Weichselian (e.g. Lehman & Forman 1992, Lauritzen 2006, Ingólfsson and Landvik 2013) and is linked to sea level changes and following tectonic uplift that still affects the study area.

Blomstrandøya (Marble Island) consists mainly of medium to high-grade metamorphic Caledonian marbles as well as pelitic schists and gneisses (e.g. Thiedig and Manby 1992, Lauritzen 2006). Thiedig and Manby (1992) as well as Lauritzen (2006) describe the Caledonian rocks striking N-S and having been affected by two synmetamorphic, co-linear phases of isoclinal folding as well as refolding by post-metamorphic crenulation to kink-folds, which are often associated with west-directed thrust faulting and imbrication.

Additionally, some small patches of unmetamorphosed, possibly Devonian, sediments are widely scattered on Marble Island (Lauritzen 2006). These sediments are either preserved in wedges associated with faulting and brecciation of the underlying marbles, or they occur in fan-shaped bodies filling channels and tubes in the marbles. Furthermore, these sediments are often injected into a mesh of calcitic veins which penetrate parts of the marbles (Thiedig and Manby 1992, Lauritzen 2006). The uplifted coastline of Marble Island is also characterised by some karstic caves which formed during the last thousands of years (Lauritzen 2006, Fig. 2).

In present geological or tectonic maps (e.g. Buggisch et al. 1992, Thiedig and Manby 1992), thrust faults or folds are not indicated within the areas of the GPR survey grids. However, we have observed several secondary features (e.g. cracks, fracture zones, or a natural slip surface) which are most likely related to fault or isostatic uplift activity (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 A recent crack probably caused by tectonic uplift that still affects Blomstrand, looking south towards Ny Ålesund. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

A question which geologists often do not stop to ask, probably because of the chasm between geological and archaeological/historical scales, but which is

crucial to this study is how much geological knowledge was available to the historical actors arriving on Blomstrand a century ago. In fact, the chemistry of marble and its geological formation did not need to be a mystery (unless one did not care to inform himself properly). In 1909, William George Renwick published 'Marble and marble working' which treated the dimension stone on a global scale. Unfortunately, the author of this report only became aware of the readily available e-book at the time of writing, so that much of its valuable information could not be included in the text. Suffice to say that a general knowledge of marble existed but that local knowledge of the resource on Blomstrand and how to work it needed to be generated on site.

Historical-archaeological setting

The English prospector Ernest Mansfield, having had some prior experience of marble quarrying, discovered Marble Island in summer 1906. Development did not start until spring 1911 and, after a voluntary absence during the First World War, only lasted until 1920.

Fig. 4 The mining settlement and quarries at Peirsonhamna, anachronically known as Ny London. The map indicates the overlap between features listed in the Askeladden database (numbered) and additional features mapped during the LASHIPA Project in 2008. (Map: F. Kruse.)

The material remains of Blomstrand are now protected, and many but not all are recognised and listed in the Askeladden database (askeladden.ra.no). In 2008, the LASHIPA Project (“Large-scale historical exploitation of polar areas”, RiS ID 3106) carried out an industrial archaeological survey of the mining settlement and quarries at Peirsonhamna (commonly but anachronically known as Ny London). The survey results have been reported in Aalders *et al.* (2009). The overlap of Askeladden and LASHIPA is indicated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 5 In 2011, Dutch researchers reported a small quarry to the south of Grottevika. (Map: F. Kruse.)

Moreover, researchers of the Netherlands Arctic Station surveyed a small historical marble quarry to the south of Grottevika in 2011. Besides an extensive mention on the Station’s weblog

(poolstation.nl), this quarry remained unreported. It currently does not have a corresponding Askeladden entry, while two claim signs of the Northern Exploration Company (commonly abbreviated to NEC) to the north of Grottevik do (Fig. 5).

Within the LASHIPA framework, Kruse (2013) investigated the activities of the Northern Exploration Co. She has been able to conclude that the history of the High Arctic marble quarries remains poorly understood and is probably unique in the polar world. Yet, the documents she has consulted to date are vague about the workability and the profitability of the natural resource. Unknown sources have been quick to pinpoint the effect of permafrost, which supposedly thawed upon transportation to warmer climates, to be the main reason behind the company's failure to exploit the dimension stone. This has been repeated uncritically in several current guide books (e.g. Hermansen 2007, 162; Umbreit 2009, 137; Johannsen 2011, 155) and has unfortunately found its way onto the internet and into many tourists' blogs. Thankfully, Stange simply refers to the quality of the marble being low due to 'many cracks' (2011, 301). Since in geology, cracks can have different origins, this statement allows room for analysis and reinterpretation. In fact, the notion of permafrost being to blame has already been investigated and discarded by Siggerud (1960). He instead proposes potentially unfavourable structural geology such as subsurface fault patterns, which would cause the marble to fail on a medium to large scale. His hypothesis had not yet been tested.

On the note of environmental consequences, it is assumed that the historical actors did not care too much about these unless their direct causes also hindered the operations and affected profitability. It is highly doubtful that any of the actors were aware of creating what is today an archaeological site, let alone having lasting and measurable effects on local ecosystems.

Methodology

Practical limitations to the fieldwork

Owing to Blomstrand's relative isolation, there were limitations to the fieldwork that could be carried out within the financial and time constraints. Most conveniently, researchers fly from the Norwegian mainland via Svalbard's capital of Longyearbyen to the scientific village of Ny Ålesund (78°55'30"N 11°55'20"E). They commonly ship any heavy or bulky equipment well in advance of the field season. The GPR equipment could not be shipped because it could not be spared by the Georadar-Forum until close to Kruse's and Koster's actual date of departure. Hence, Koster was forced to reduce the weight and size of the equipment, including his personal belongings, to approximately 40kg. This still exceeded the very strict allowance of 20kg per person on flights between Longyearbyen and Ny Alesund, but timely registration with Kings Bay AS and paying for the excess luggage took care of this. The informal suggestion of taking a chance with more equipment since occasionally flights are not fully booked was immediately disregarded. Having a very narrow fieldwork window of only seven days, we could not risk any of our equipment not reaching Ny Ålesund and in turn Blomstrand. As a result, Koster worked with only one antenna instead of the usual range of three antennae. Kruse had prepared to take a Differential Global Positioning System (dGPS) to Blomstrand. She was aware that Ny Ålesund is a 'radio silent area', a fact that is drummed into any visitor in the possession of a mobile phone. However, in the absence of easily accessible details about this radio silence or a map of its extent, she did not realise that the area extended across Kongsfjorden to Blomstrand. She was hence not permitted to use the dGPS and needed to borrow an unfamiliar instrument. Unfortunately, this instrument, while clearly indicating altitude on the screen, failed to record the important data, which undermined the results and success of the fieldwork.

Ground-penetrating radar(GPR) survey at the quarries, conducted by B. Koster

In 2008, members of the LASHIPA Project observed a substantial fracture zone in the historical Winter Quarry (1919/20) on Blomstrand (Fig. 6). They were also able to trace several cracks on nearby outcrop surfaces. Although this fault may have been an obvious reason behind this particular quarry's abandonment, it was outside the scope of their fieldwork to examine this assumption further.

Between July 12 and 16, 2014, a ground penetrating radar (GPR) survey was therefore carried out to investigate these and other possible zones of weakness such as cracks, faults, and holes in the subsurface. A medium-frequency antenna promised to be the best compromise between the spatial resolution of any cracks or faults, and the achievable penetration depth. As can be seen in Appendix 1, A1.1, we used a GSSI 400MHz antenna with a survey wheel, a SIR-3000 data acquisition system,

and a handheld GPS. Trace increment was set to 0.02m in order to achieve a high data density; the range was set to 90ns TWT with a sample rate of 1024. Using the 400MHz GPR antenna, a GPR target depth of approximately 4m could be aimed for.

Fig. 6 A fault and a natural slip surface observed in a historical quarry on Blomstrand in 2008. (Photo: D. Avango.)

The number of GPR survey grids was dependent on the time spent on site, which in turn dependent on weather and ice conditions as well as transport arrangements between Ny Ålesund and Blomstrand. The positioning of the grids was guided by previously known historical quarry and borehole locations (Appendix A1.2). Ultimately, seven GPR survey grids were laid out in such a way as to allow for the best comparison of historical information and subsequent GPR data (Figs. 7 and 8). The most relevant historical data that was known prior to the fieldwork has been summarized in Appendices A1.3 and A1.4.

The number of GPR survey grids was dependent on the time spent on site, which in turn dependent on weather and ice conditions as well as transport arrangements

Fig. 7 GPR survey grids 1 to 5. Grid 1 was positioned immediately west of the Winter Quarry (1919/20). Grid 2 was positioned south of both the Winter Quarry and Grid 1. The two x's between mark the boreholes B1-68 (left) and B2-68 (right), which were drilled in 1968. Grid 3 was positioned on a marble outcrop near No. 2 Quarry, the x here marking a borehole sunk in winter 1912/13. Grid 4 was positioned immediately west of No. 3 Quarry opened in summer 1912. Grid 5 was positioned immediately

east of the same. The x's mark a borehole probably drilled in winter 1912/13 (south) and borehole B5-68 sunk in 1968 (north). (Map: F. Kruse.)

Fig. 8 GPR survey grids 6 and 7.

Grid 6 was positioned immediately north of Quarry A13 opened in spring 1920. Grid 7 was positioned on a marble outcrop that comprised two boreholes sunk in summer 1920. (Map: F. Kruse.)

Additional details of the GPR survey grids 1 to 7 are provided in Fig. 9 below. A spacing of 1m was chosen, with which 125 GPR

profiles were completed. Using Surfer 11 (Golden Software), it was subsequently possible to reconstruct pseudo-3D subsurface models visualizing weakness zones in the marble (e.g. Grandjean & Gourry 1996; Godio et al. 2003).

Fig. 9 Details of the seven GPR survey grids. A spacing of 1m was used, and 125 profiles were completed. (Figure: B. Koster.)

To give an indication of the raw data collected, a contact sheet of all 125 profiles has been included in Appendix 1.5. General GPR data processing was then carried out with ReflexW V7.5 (Sandmeier Scientific Software) and included static correction, back-ground removal, gain adjustments, and velocity adaption for time-depth conversions. The latter was based on a hyperbola analysis where such features were present. Additionally, we used characteristic velocities based on the subsurface material, which in this study is marble (Grandjean & Gourry 1996; Neal & Roberts 2000; Neal 2004; Sambuelli & Calzoni 2010). A contact sheet of the processed images is included in Appendix A1.6. Cracks and faults were detected due to hyperbolic features and abruptly shifted continuous reflectors in the data (e.g. Grandjean & Gourry 1996; Godio et al. 2003; Sambuelli & Calzoni 2010). For some grids, the GPR data can partly be correlated with quarries opened by the Northern Exploration Co. in the early 20th century in order to verify and trace the detected cracks and faults. Photo documentation, study area description, and levelling of the study areas were also carried out in the field. Appendix 2 comprises a full photographic record of the fieldwork. Additionally, historical boreholes were calibrated by handheld GPS to compare historical borehole logs with GPR data at these locations.

Vegetation survey in the former mining settlement, conducted by M. Loonen

It was known from historical sources that the Northern Exploration Co. had imported livestock for the provision of fresh meat. Pigs were present on site in summer 1912, the last of that lot being slaughtered in December, and cattle was landed in June 1913 (Booth 1913). The photograph below (Fig. 10) was taken at the back of the settlement, looking southeast, probably prior to the construction of the storehouse. Dogs were kept for company, too. Humans, pigs, cows, hay, and to a lesser extent dogs may have had a measurable impact on the local vegetation.

Fig. 10 Cattle attempting to graze at the back of the mining settlement on Blomstrand. They are also being feed hay. (Source: Barr et al 2011, 103.)

Independently of Kruse and Koster, Maarten Loonen visited the former mining

settlement on Blomstrand on a number of occasions between June and August 2014. On these occasions, he studied the local vegetation as a component of the terrestrial ecosystem. 'Local' not being strictly defined, it loosely refers to the vicinity of the upstanding houses as well as the barrack and storehouse foundations at a radius of +/- 10m.

At the beginning of the season in June, Loonen erected several pairs of chicken-wire vegetation enclosures (50cm x 50cm x 50cm) around the former settlement. Their locations are marked on the map in Appendix A3.1. The vegetation enclosures have the function of preventing any grazing and trampling of the vegetation by 'excluding', for example, geese and reindeer (Fig. 11). The enclosures were placed next to (but not on) selected barrack entrances, and their controls were positioned approximately 6m away. In these enclosures, labelled A11, A12, A13, A14, A15, and A17, production was measured on grass tillers at the end of the season on August 4, 2014. Thereafter, the installations were removed without leaving a trace in the field.

Fig. 11 Reindeer passing by an inconspicuous chicken-wire vegetation enclosure, emphasising the effectiveness of the temporary installation. (Photo: B. Koster.)

On July 12, 16, and 20, 2014, Loonen additionally carried out visual surveys of the unenclosed vegetation in the mining settle-

ment in order to describe the local plant assemblages and to map any newly appearing species. He took small samples of these plants for identification and DNA-barcoding.

As this was a pilot study and time was limited, the quarries, the railway embankments, and other zones of industrial activity were not studied this year.

Reconnaissance dive in Peirsonhamna, conducted by M. Schwanitz

A reconnaissance dive was conducted in the small bay of Peirsonhamna by Mr Max Schwanitz and a team of divers of the Alfred-Wegener-Institut (AWI) based at Ny Ålesund between June 24 and July 10, 2014. The approximate position of the natural harbour is 78°57'41.06"N and 12°2'38.83"E (Fig. 4). It is roughly circular, measuring between 250m and 300m both in east-west direction and in north-south direction. Depending on the state of the tide, the maximum water depth is between 6m and 7m. It opens into Kongsfjorden to the south.

The team investigated Peirsonhamna on four occasions, completing a total of eight dives in accordance to the GUV regulations “Einsatz von Forschungstauchern” (BGR / GUV-R 2112, issue 2011). The divers made use of an anchoring vessel and a lifeline. The dive times were between 27 and 53 minutes. The maximum depth was 6.2m.

Finds were marked by small buoys and ground weights. Subsequently – when possible – they were photographed, measured, and occasionally drawn.

Mr Schwanitz provided a detailed report in German, which has been added in Appendix 4.

Newly recorded archaeology on Blomstrand, conducted by F. Kruse

While the planned interdisciplinary site work was progressing, Kruse took the opportunity to build on the archaeological knowledge of the former mining settlement and quarries as indicated in Figs 4 and 5 above. By means of a walkover, she was able to confirm the majority of the observations and interpretations of the LASHIPA Project in 2008 and newly recorded additional archaeological features, thereby creating a more comprehensive image of the site and its site formation processes. Furthermore, Kruse and Koster took time away from the GPR survey to ascend Ingensfjellet, Blomstrand’s highest peak at 383m AOD and rounded the island on its west side. The hike served the purpose of mapping any material remains not listed in the Askeladden database, thereby populating the archaeological landscape. Any documentation pertaining to newly recorded archaeological features has been included in Appendix 5.

Kruse also experimented with a metal detector. She had not asked *sysselmannen* for permission to do this and hence none had been given. While metal objects could thus be located non-intrusively beneath the surface, it was strictly forbidden to dig them up and identify them. So the point of metal detecting was primarily one of testing the method under Arctic circumstances as a useful tool to identify specific areas of metal-related activities. This befits a landscape approach to Svalbard archaeology.

Kruse first attempted a metal detector survey on the beach in Peirsonhamna. This is best done at the lowest tide and by working parallel to the shore, not at an angle. If the tide is going out, one can start at the top of the beach and follow the water out. If the tide is coming in, one can start at the water’s edge and work landwards. Coloured survey flags are suitable for marking locations that give off signals. They are handy for marking ‘spot finds’, and they are equally handy for probing the concealed edges of large structural metal. In addition, they are very visible in photographs, the only recording of the detected locations that was done on this occasion in light of the disallowed dGPS. Where structural metal needed to be ‘followed’, wooden toothpicks were used: they do not give off a signal themselves and are short enough to survey over the top of. A subsequent ‘joining of dots’ reveals the extent of the item (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 Toothpicks were used during non-intrusive metal detecting in Peirsonhamna in order to trace the extent of concealed structural metal. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

Limited time and an unexpected overload of signals in Peirsonhamna led to the abandonment of the first attempt. A second effort was made and completed on a 'less

busy' beach in the first small bay to the east of Peirsonhamna. No metal detecting was carried out in the former mining settlement and industrial areas. These were assumed to be 'too busy' to give useful results.

Archival research in Great Britain, conducted by F. Kruse

Strictly speaking, the fieldwork and the archival research in the UK occurred separately, but it makes sense to combine and include the findings and preliminary interpretations of the latter in this report, even if it does swell the pages. By means of introduction, the author has made an effort to repeat some of the many known historical photographs in Appendix A6.1.

"Marble at Fault" being a multi-phased project, Kruse actually intended continued archival research in both the UK as well as North America. Firstly, her documentary leads suggested that another reason for the company's failure may have been a depression in the British marble market caused by significant changes as a result of the First World War, particularly a governmental subsidy of affordable housing development rather than luxury building. Secondly, machinery remaining on Marble Island today was manufactured and supplied by the US firms Sullivan and Ingersoll-Rand, which proves the company's efforts in the direction of America. This finds verification in historical documents that also tell of a directorial visit to New York in 1912 in order to size up the American marble market, enlist the help of marble specialists here, and enrol further investors. Archival research in this direction could potentially reveal the reasons why subsidiary companies, which were envisaged to carry out actual mining, never come forward.

Most importantly, the original hand-written manuscript, notebook, and diary of Herbert Leech, marble manager for the first time in summer 1919 (and then again in summer 1920), survive in Toronto, Canada, awaiting auction for the phenomenal sum approaching \$9.900. This sum is

probably related to a mention of Shackleton, who is of great interest to collectors, although he never actually arrived on Spitsbergen. Kruse hoped to obtain the cooperation of the current owner and gain access to these papers in order to tap into their academic potential. Unfortunately, the owner felt that he had nothing to gain from such a cooperation. Kruse never saw the papers, and their value for this research remains unknown.

After the fieldwork in autumn 2014, Kruse conducted additional archival research in Great Britain. Following up leads arising from her previous study, she visited the following repositories:

- The National Archives of Scotland, Edinburgh
- The National Mining Museum of Scotland, Newtongrange
- The North of England Institute of Mining and Metallurgy Library, Newcastle-upon-Tyne

In addition to consulting a broad but limited range of primary documentary sources, she met with Mr David Newman, a local historian in Goldhanger, Essex, who provided valuable information about Ernest Mansfield and others who had once resided in the village while at the same time being instrumental to the Northern Exploration Co. and to the marble quarries on Blomstrand. Moreover, she accessed *The Times*, *The Gazette*, and *Hansard* (the UK parliamentary record) online.

The material relating to historical marble quarrying thereby discovered was sparse, but it opened new lines of enquiry and occasionally led to unexpected results.

At the time of writing, Kruse became aware that an important contemporary text had become available online. In 1909, Renwick published an extensive account of marble and marble working around the globe. Unfortunately, Kruse did not have time to work through the text and include any relevant aspects in this report. A quick glance, however, revealed that Renwick apparently did not know about the marble quarries at Fauske in Norway. This and other historical details of marble and marble workings are included in Appendix 6.

Results

Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) survey

The GPR survey generated a total of 125 GPR profiles with lengths between 10m and 40 m in seven different survey grids. Survey grids 1 to 7 were located close to known historical quarries and/or boreholes (Fig. 13). All GPR measurements were acquired on outcrop surfaces of the bedrock, i.e. not on any unconsolidated overburden overlying the marble, to ensure direct coupling with features in the subsurface. The GPR profiles were mainly recorded at right angles to continuous cracks, faults, or fracture zones that were observed on the ground surface or in historical quarries as indicated in Fig. 13. Due to particularly strong continuous reflectors visible in the raw data of Grid 7, GPR profiles were carried out in both perpendicular and parallel directions. The weather conditions on the days prior to and during the survey were arid and mostly sunny with temperatures between -8°C and $+5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The survey grids and surrounds were free of snow, ice, or water retention.

The main hyperbolae velocities in the GPR data range between 0.09 m/ns and 0.10 m/ns, which is similar to electromagnetic wave velocities given in literature for marble rocks (e.g. Grandjean and Gourry 1996, Neal and Roberts 2000, Neal 2004, Sambuelli and Calzoni 2010).

Fig. 13 Settings of survey grids 1 to 7 (orange outlines with correspondingly numbered corners), any adjacent quarries (grey areas) and boreholes (red points), and observed cracks on outcrop surfaces (dashed lines). The black arrows indicate zigzagging GPR profiles, of which the blue ones indicate the start of the survey as well as the main direction for processing. (Figure: B. Koster.)

Survey grids 1 and 2:

The area under investigation in survey grids 1 and 2 is located to the west and southwest of the Winter Quarry opened in winter 1919/20 (Fig. 7). In this quarry, a fault and a natural slip surface were observed (Fig. 6; Fig. 13A; Appendix A1.4).

Fig. 14 Locations of observed crack or fault features within the subsurface of survey grids 1 and 2 as well as two boreholes of 1968 (red rhombi). (A) Cracks and fractured zones visible at the surface (left, green circles) and cracks and fractured zones only detected within the subsurface (right, grey circles) using GPR (generally, the size of the circles increases with depth to ~4m below the surface); (B) Grids 1 and 2 visualised in a pseudo-3D model (colours as before, while point size is constant). (Figure: B. Koster.)

The grids were surveyed in different directions due to the NW-SE trending of the fault and with the objective to visualise additional structures as effectively as possible (Fig. 14A). The fault zone can be traced throughout the whole of the GPR data for Grid 1 as well as Grid 2 from NNW to SSE and approaching the maximum survey depths of ~4m (Fig. 14B).

Abruptly shifted reflectors in the GPR data as well as small vertically aligned hyperbolae reflections with velocities around 0.09m/ns indicate fracturing of the marble. In some parts, the cracks are branched in various directions, which is not visible from the ground surface but detectable by GPR. In this survey area, a lot of vertical cracks that are not visible from ground surface (starting at a minimum depth of 0.4m below the ground surface) were observed in the GPR data. These cracks are aligned and branched in several directions emerging chaotic fracture structures. Within both survey grids, only small parts are free from cracks and faults fracturing the marble.

Survey grid 3:

The area under investigation in Grid 3 is located ~300m to the SSW of Grids 1 and 2 at the end of the former railway embankment and incorporates a historical borehole drilled and cemented in winter 1912/13 (Fig. 7; Fig. 13B; Appendix A1.3). Interestingly, the borehole had been sunk into one of two linear cracks visible on ground surface along the eastern and western edges of the survey grid. Between these cracks, homogenous conditions of the marble could potentially exist. The GPR survey direction was thus chosen to be perpendicular to the linear cracks on the surface. The two main cracks at the east and west edge of the survey grid clearly show in the GPR data up to ~4m depth below ground surface (Fig. 15A). In the northern part of the survey grid, the GPR also detected several small vertical cracks in the subsurface.

Fig. 15 Locations of observed crack or fault features within the subsurface of Grid 3 as well as a borehole sunk in 1912/13 (red rhomb). (A) Faults and cracks traced from ground surface (greenish points) and detected fractured zones and folds only within the subsurface (greyish points) using GPR (in general: small points = near ground surface; bigger points = up to 4m depth below surface); (B) Similar survey grid visualised in a pseudo-3D model with illustration of observed multiple folds in the marble bedrock from slightly different viewing directions (colours of points indicate same characteristics as previously mentioned while point size is constant). (Figure: B. Koster.)

Unexpectedly, the GPR data indicate two blended folds with several branched cracks (Fig. 15B). The top of the upper fold is located only $\sim 0.3\text{m}$ below ground surface. The folds are characterised by relatively clear and continuous reflectors with sporadic linear adjacent hyperbolae reflections (velocities $\sim 0.09\text{m/ns}$). Hence, the marble within Grid 3 is seriously fractured due to the folds and adjacent fracture zones as well as several scattered vertical cracks.

Survey grids 4 and 5:

The areas under investigation in survey grids 4 and 5 are located only ~30m NE of grids 1 and 2 on either side of the historical No. 3 Quarry opened in 1912 (Fig. 7; Fig. 13C; Appendix A1.4). There is also a historical borehole sunk in winter 1912/13 (Appendix 1.3) and another one from 1968 (currently no known record). The GPR survey was carried out parallel to the direction of channeling (quarrying by machine) and perpendicular to a long crack visible on the marble's surface. The GPR data in both areas are slightly overdriven, and cracks as well as fault features are challenging to observe. The cracks visible on the surface (marked) can be followed by several small hyperbolae as well as displaced continuous reflectors, which most likely indicate a fault (Figs. 16 & 17). The depth of this feature can be observed up to the lower end (~4m depth below ground surface) of the GPR data. Furthermore, a smooth continuous reflector at ~2m depth below ground surface is observed in northern part of Grid 4. This feature possibly indicates an internal boundary or a dislocated surface within the marble. In some GPR profiles, smooth reflection patterns with several small hyperbolae are observed. These structures maybe indicate chaotic fracturing areas in the subsurface. It is not clear whether these belong to crack features near the ground surface or possibly internal alteration/weathering of the marble. Beside the main fault within survey grids 4 and 5, there are several small (vertical) fracturing features visible. It remains challenging to interpret cracks at both investigation areas due to the slightly overdriven data quality.

Fig. 16 GPR profile 69 recorded within survey grid 4: (A) processed GPR profile, (B) processed and analysed GPR profile and (C) interpretation of the GPR profile. (Figure: B. Koster.)

Fig. 17 GPR profile 78 recorded within survey grid 5: (A) processed GPR profile, (B) processed and analysed GPR profile and (C) interpretation of the GPR profile. (Figure: B. Koster.)

Survey grid 6:

The area under investigation in Grid 6 is located ~1.5km NW of the other survey grids and next to a historical quarry known from a single historical source only as Quarry A13 opened either in winter 1919/20 or in spring 1920 (Fig. 8; Appendix A1.4). In the field, we called it the Western or Lighthouse Quarry due to the modern beacon nearby. The survey grid was positioned at right angles to the direction of mining but also perpendicular to a linear crack on the marble's surface (Fig. 13D). The GPR data comprise several discontinued reflectors as well as several single hyperbolae reflections. Linear surface cracks marked in the GPR data can be traced by slightly shifted reflectors in the GPR data as well as aligned hyperbolae reflections up to ~3.5m depth below ground surface (Fig. 18). Further vertical cracks can be linked to linear hyperbolae reflections or shifted discontinued reflectors in the marble. Altogether the marble in this investigation area seems not as affected by damaging of the marble due to fractures and cracks, although some fracturing of the marble in the adjacent surface works can be observed.

Fig. 18 GPR profile 102 recorded within survey grid 6: (A) processed GPR profile, (B) processed and analysed GPR profile and (C) interpretation of the GPR profile. (Figure: B. Koster.)

A close inspection of the shallow surface works were carried out and showed what happened when a line of drilled holes (a method of channeling) met with a natural fracture (Figs 19a-c).

Fig. 19a Tool marks in Quarry A13. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

Fig. 19b The circle indicates a plant that grew at the point at which the line of holes was stopped by the nature feature and abandoned. The arrow marks a borehole brought forward from the original line, but drilling was not commenced from here. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

Fig. 19c A plant grew at the point at which the line of holes was stopped by the fracture or fault and abandoned. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

In addition, the depths of individual holes were measured to get an idea of the effort that when into drilling them (Fig. 20).

Hole	Depth	Hole	Depth										
1	17	8	67	15	83	22	82	29	92	36	56	43	90
2	49	9	75	16	87	23	76	30	68	37	62	44	106
3	45	10	75	17	n/a	24	89	31	85	38	71	45	90
4	53	11	n/a	18	n/a	25	n/a	32	85	39	84	46	90
5	55	12	68	19	90	26	95	33	88	40	84		
6	58	13	n/a	20	n/a	27	94	34	69	41	84	Total	2957
7	62	14	87	21	n/a	28	93	35	64	42	89		

Fig. 20 Individual and total depths (in mm) of holes in Quarry A13. The bottom of some holes could not be observed and the last attempts were not taken into consideration, the total effort was therefore several meters larger than 29.57m.

Survey grid 7:

The area investigated in Grid 7 is located ~40m to the N of Grid 6 and Quarry A13. It comprises two historical boreholes sunk in summer 1920 (Fig. 8; Appendix A1.4). Leech (1920) described one as a 3-inch hole (7.6cm) and the other 4-inch (10.2cm) and that both had been drilled to 7 feet (2.13m), where the marble crumbled due to a suspected subsurface fault. It was surprising, however, that the holes were found to be separated by a few centimeters only (Fig. 21). The smaller one was found to be 2m deep, the larger 1.9m, which is close enough to the depths stated. The level of liquid water was recorded at 1.47m bgl.

Fig. 21 Leech (1920) described two boreholes being drilled in summer 1920. These were found to be separated by a few cm only. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

A linear crack running SW-NE could be seen at the surface (Fig. 13E). GPR data reveals a strong continuous reflector in both the perpendicular and the parallel profile. These reflectors are accompanied by further hyperbolae ($v = 0.09\text{m/ns}$) that are chaotically distributed alongside the continuous reflector. Pseudo-3D visualization of picked GPR data (Fig. 22) indicate a fold structure with its fold axis near the surface ($\sim 0.2\text{m}$ depth below ground surface) and is most likely the reason for the linear crack observed at the surface. It is obvious that the marble in this survey grid is fractured due to the present fold structure with a surrounding fracture zone with a diameter of $\sim 0.5\text{m}$.

Fig. 22 Location and orientation of observed fold within the subsurface of survey grid 7 as well as location of two boreholes (red rhomb): (A) Contour map of the observed fold with data points (greenish points; constant point size in different depths) as well as location of boreholes (red rhombi) within the survey grid; (B) Similar survey grid visualised in a pseudo-3D model: (top) 3D data points (constant point size) and (bottom) 3D contour model. (Figure: B. Koster.)

Vegetation survey

At the time of writing, it is possible to include a map of the mining settlement indicating the locations of newly appearing plant species (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23 The results of the visual vegetation survey in the former mining settlement show newly appearing plants (dots, circles = individual plants, shading = high density of plants). (Data: M. Loonen. Map: F. Kruse.)

It is clear from the map that newly appearing plants can mainly be found in the immediate vicinity of former and current buildings, in particular around former and especially current doorways, as opposed to more open areas or the vicinity to water. The assumption is that newly appearing species found their way here as seeds on the shoes or in the clothing of visitors or in animal feed such as hay. The highest densities occur around the upstanding buildings that used to be managerial accommodation (A). These high densities are thought to be the compound result of historical activities, cruise tourism, and overnight stays, which are still possible in the huts. Due to ongoing site formation processes, these areas do not lend themselves to temporal analysis.

The question arises if anywhere on site lends itself to historically-relevant analysis, since visitors have been and are free to go anywhere they please, and the potential of continued seed introduction exists across the whole site if not island. However, some places are more attractive to visitors than others and the simple wooden platforms are thought to rate extremely low in this list of attractive places. Therefore, the pattern of newly appearing species around the doorways of the former barracks is thought to be a historical pattern. The plants are likely to have been brought by the builders and miners.

A conspicuous concentration and spread can be seen around the particular former barrack behind which the historical photograph of the cows was taken (B). Again, there is no specific reason why cruise tourists and overnight visitors should linger here. So the observations support the notion that cows, other livestock, and hay were kept in this area. And that their manure may have enriched the soil and enhanced production. That has yet to be confirmed.

The former storehouse in which the historical channelers and other machinery have now been gathered (C) is, on the other hand, a very poignant location and immediately appeals to many visitors. Being a hotspot of ongoing tourism, it is impossible to say much about the newly appearing plants here.

Fig. 24 A stone-lined drain down to the stream. (Photo: D. Avango.)

It is noticeable that former toilets are not immediately obvious on the site. From historical photographs, the workers' lavatories are known to have been incorporated into the barrack doorways, and a similar

construction probably existed in the managerial houses. Lavatories are again interesting from an 'enriching the soil' perspective. Even if they were indoor toilets, the buckets must have been emptied somewhere, and it was thought that the features marked D could have been stone-lined drains for this purpose. However, they were remarkably devoid of grasses or any other newly appearing plants. To supplement the visual survey, the measurements of grass tillers in the vegetation exclosures and in nearby unexclosed areas have been provided in Appendix A3.2. The analysis of the vegetation survey had not yet been completed.

Reconnaissance dive

The team of divers discovered an overseeable number of metal objects at two of four dive locations in Peirsonhamna. Below the crane, they found a small metal wheel (probably a machine part), a length of rail, a metal rod to tie rails together, a tool (probably a crowbar), and two metal plates. Below the Norwegian fishery station, they recorded a small hoist, a metal bracket to pin wooden sleepers together, and a non-descript metal object. In the stream delta and in mid-harbour, they saw nothing. Besides metal objects, there were no other forms of clearly visible impacts under water. A full report is provided in Appendix 4.

Newly recorded archaeology

Any newly recorded archaeology has been included in Appendix 5. It comprises a map of features, a list of observations and preliminary interpretations, and a photograph of the calendar from 1968. The map below summaries the results of the walk over and around half of Blomstrand. All archaeological features encountered were mapped (Fig. 25). Besides former industrial features already mentioned in the text, these comprised exclusively fox traps.

Fig. 25 Map showing the walk over and around one half of Blomstrand, indicating all archaeological remains not previously mentioned in the text. These were exclusively fox traps. (Map: B. Koster.)

The experimental metal detector survey was inconclusive. While the method lends itself to Arctic conditions, permission must be sought to use it properly. The beach in Peirsonhamna could not be

surveyed completely in the time available. The next beach along was small and surveyed completely. There were signs of the recent human presence in Svalbard in the form of washed-up broken plastic as well as two pieces of orange peel and a whole apple. Metal was detected in the form of two nails in a small piece of driftwood and a bullet cartridge. Significantly, they corresponded to the two main activities expected from this: construction and hunting. There is hope for better results in other areas in the future.

Archival research

New information discovered in the archives as well as on the internet has been included in Appendix 6. This includes repeat photography, the contents of archival sources and their preliminary interpretation placed in a crude timeline, Home Office marble statistics between the years 1902 and 1912, summaries of two company files, and a summary of the environmental impact and diseases of a wintering party in 1912/13.

Discussion, conclusion, and future work

The interdisciplinary archaeological fieldwork that was carried out at the former British mining settlement and quarries on Blomstrand in Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen, in July 2014 addressed two main questions, which shall be dealt with in turn.

1) Why did past attempts to quarry marble on this Arctic island fail?

The assumption that permafrost had a negative effect on the marble is simply wrong. A focus on purely geological factors is inexcusably short-sighted. In industrial archaeology and mining history, one must make a habit of considering a combination of geological factors, managerial and/or directorial flaws, and market forces at work. One or more of these may weigh more heavily than the others.

Regarding potential geological factors, a GPR survey was carried out in order to assess the quality of the marble that had been explored and worked historically. The survey established seven grids (125 profiles). Grids 1 and 2 substantiated the considerable fault zone clearly visible in the Winter Quarry of 1919/20, which had for that obvious reason been abandoned in 1920 – the data showed that further work in the immediate vicinity would have been uneconomical. Grid 3 was close to No. 2 Quarry opened in 1912 and incorporated a borehole sunk in 1912/13, from which only rubble was then retrieved. The borehole lay on a visible crack. The crack was caused by an underlying fold, along the limbs of which extensive fracturing had occurred – working would probably have been uneconomical. Grids 4 and 5 lay on either side of No. 3 Quarry opened in 1912, about which the marble manager continued to be enthusiastic in 1920. The smooth continuous reflector at a depth of ~2m, practically surface rock, might or might not have been disruptive during working – the results remain inconclusive. Grid 6 to one side of Quarry A13 opened in 1920 displayed some surface cracks that seemed to discontinue at depth – the marble was seemingly sound, but Grid 7 lay uncomfortably close by. Grid 7 comprised two boreholes sunk in 1920, which were known to have hit a fault that was, however, not thought to be worrying. In fact, the grid revealed a substantial fold with a 50-cm fracture zone around the limbs – this may have been potentially workable if any quarrying were orientated appropriately. To make the most of the GPR results, they will in the near future be discussed with marble quarry specialists.

In light of the above, we can currently say that we were able to detect several cracks, faults, fractured zones, and even (multiple) folds on the archaeological scale, as opposed to a geological one, to a depth of up to ~4m below ground level using GPR with only the 400 MHz antenna instead of a range of three antennae. The orientation of cracks, faults, and folds varies strongly within all survey grids. Therefore, not all features may be related to major thrust faults and folding on

Blomstrand. However, the majority of cracks and faults in the marble were not recognisable from the ground surface, which addresses one of the main issues at the heart of the GPR investigations.

Approximately a century ago, the different actors involved in the exploration and quarrying of the marble, irrespective of the nature of their 'loyalty' to the Northern Exploration Co., were most likely not able to detect the amount of "damage" within the marble by means of boreholes and shallow surveys. Structural information (like fractured marble) might have been noted in historical borehole logs but in a different way from modern technical capabilities and due to missing information about detailed subsurface architecture.

Present geological or tectonic maps still do not show faults in the areas where the mining company tried excavating the marble, which is possibly due to the large scale of geological mapping of Blomstrand. A lot of faults are assumed to be related to isostatic uplift as we were able to observe several fresh surface cracks in different orientations. Isostatic uplift has been active since the Late Weichselian (e.g. Lehman & Forman 1992, Lauritzen 2006, Ingólfsson and Landvik 2013) in Kongsfjorden. Detailed geological mapping, especially structural/tectonic information, in the vicinity of former mining areas on Blomstrand could be an additional tool for a better understanding of the subsurface conditions.

In general, the GPR technique seems to be capable of detecting faults and similar features of the bedrock in an Arctic environment. Former studies have already illustrated GPR investigations on marble quarries but under Mediterranean weather conditions (e.g. Grandjean and Gourry 1996, Godio et al. 2003). However, subsurface investigations of the marble of Blomstrand is possible providing excellent Arctic summer conditions (temperatures around 0°C, arid, no snow cover or water detention on the bedrock, no permafrost soil coverage) as well as using the appropriate GPR setup and an investigation-matching antenna frequency (in this study 400 MHz). A lower frequency antenna (e.g. 270 MHz or 200 MHz) could possibly detect cracks and faults even in lower depths, but resolution would be worse (e.g. Neal 2004) and, therefore, smaller cracks and faults might not be visible in the GPR data.

Besides the quality of the marble, managerial incompetence on site may have been another factor. Archaeologically, this may out itself in overspending on superficial structures prior to World War I. As Kruse (2013) has already pointed out, the mining settlement seemed rather impressive in relation to the limited quarrying done, but this may have been part of an advertising strategy to present far-away investors with exciting Arctic photographs and entice them into investing further into this grand scheme. No buildings were erected after the war and little remains of the large radio antenna that was put up, so it may not be immediately obvious whether overspending continued. Away from Blomstrand, however, elsewhere on Spitsbergen, the NEC definitely spent more money than it made

in return. Overspending was a serious flaw, but if the company had actually delivered raw materials in large, profitable amounts, it could yet have been worth it. So overspending was a relative. More importantly, the archival sources point to several crucial things. Firstly, there appears to have been a growing demand for marble prior to the First World War. This would have been a sensible time to invest in the resource. Secondly, however, the diamond coring in 1912/13 had not been successful (sabotage was mentioned, but Booth's own technical abilities were not questioned), yet beautiful solid cores mysteriously appeared in the London office. It is also suspicious that the crucial report by the American marble specialist Minard, who worked on site in summer 1913, can no longer be found. Was it willfully destroyed? This hints at fraud, but it cannot be proven who was responsible. Was it Mansfield? Was it Salisbury-Jones? It certainly appears to have been someone in the field as it seems that the directors truly believed in the soundness and value of their marble. Even when the market crashed after the war and when the Danish Commissioner raised a fee for every acre claimed, the company hung on to Blomstrand. It remained in the possession of the company, until it sold all its assets to the Norwegian Government.

All things considered, crash in the marble market was the main reason for all work being suspended in 1920 – at a point when it had not been proven beyond all doubt whether the marble was or was not workable, let alone profitable. Trying to prove this beyond the GPR survey carried out during the project 'Marble at Fault' is not necessary: since the historical actors had no knowledge of the resource beyond that which is included in these pages; new geological knowledge beyond the reach of the historical works is probably very interesting but loses its historical relevance. However, Minard's report of 1913 or the borehole logs of 1968 could fill the current knowledge gap.

2) What was the lasting impact of this industry on the local environment?

The construction, exploring, and quarrying activities on Blomstrand between 1911 and 1920 created the cultural heritage that is protected by law today. This in itself is an obvious long-lasting environmental impact. Although some people find polar industrial heritage unsightly, it is a reminder of past human endeavour in this location. If a dGPS had been available, Kruse and Koster would have attempted to quantify the volume of earth and rock that had been moved around on site. This would have been the direct impact of construction and quarrying.

The metal detector survey which Kruse tried was meant to delineate subtle zones of metal-related activities, but this failed due to an unexpected overload of signals, i.e. a large number of metal objects in the ground. The question remains how much scrap metal the site actually comprises. It is bound to be a lot. So what is its environmental impact?

In the framework of “Consequences of exploitation”, the vegetation in the mining settlement was investigated by means of a walkover survey and in the form of production on grass tillers. The resultant map clearly indicates the distribution of newly appearing species, mainly grasses, which can be shown to have historical relevance. This pilot study can and should be built on: a comprehensive systematic study should be undertaken across the settlement as well as the industrial areas to map, identify, and qualify all newly appearing species. This has to a certain extent been done in places like Longyearbyen and Ny Ålesund. Unlike these places, Marble Island had a limited ‘life span’ that practically ended not necessarily in 1920 but at the time when the barracks were removed to Ny Ålesund. Having a definite beginning and fairly definite end makes a historical site a better case study for lasting environmental impact of certain activities than an open-ended place, where changes are ongoing. An analysis of the production on grass tillers has yet to show if livestock has caused an enrich of the soil in certain location on Blomstrand.

Besides some large metal objects being found under water, the quarrying does not seem to have had any lasting effects on the coastal ecosystem. It was hoped that rubbish heaps could perhaps be located at the bottom of the cliffs, but this was not so.

The Day Book written by the mechanic David Booth in winter 1912/13 and a mention by Herbert Leech in 1920 that 11 men wintered that time offered an unusual glimpse into the environmental impact of such a group on the marine and terrestrial ecosystems. In itself, the removal of 100+ birds and a handful of seals may not seem significant, but if more historical accounts of this type were known and analysed, a comprehensive picture of the impact of the human presence could over time emerge. It would take a lot of work, but it would be invaluable. It is interesting that Booth does not make a mention of reindeer and polar bears. They had probably been hunted to the extent of being absent from the Kongsfjorden area.

Booth does, however, mention the presence of trappers in the camp. The nature of hunting on the island was briefly addressed by Kruse and Koster during the walk over and around the island. Even the simple plotting of fox traps encountered gives form to an emerging archaeological landscape of hunting and trapping. This should also be pursued further and in better resolution.

While Kruse and Koster were on site, they were regularly visited by a handful of reindeer, three long-tailed skuas, and an Arctic fox. They also observed several common eider ducks with chicks and two barnacle geese on the beach in Peirsonhamna. They discovered a single old eider duck nest. Animals further away than could be identified without binoculars have been disregarded in this tally.

This account of the site’s lasting environmental impact is piecemeal, but it reflects the nature of the sources very well and indicates what kind of questions can and need to be asked of this form of qualitative data. It takes much effort to transform archaeological and anecdotal evidence into an ecologically meaningful account.

Outreach

Good science does good outreach ☺

Svalbardposten

“Marble at Fault” benefitted from the early attention of *Svalbardposten*, probably based on the simple curiosity that the author shared her first name with Frigg Jørgensen of AECO, who had also been granted financial support of the Svalbard Environmental Protection Fund in the 2013. Following a telephone interview with Christian Nicolai Bjørke, the article ‘Frigga får oppfly marmordrømmen’ introduced the project to readers in issue number 47 of November 29, 2013. (Appendix A7.1)

Svalbardposten was also instrumental in advertising the workshop in Longyearbyen in January 2014 (see below). A copy of the advertisement, which additionally functioned as a poster to be displayed in strategic locations and online, can be found in the Appendix A7.2.

Upon arrival in Longyearbyen in July 2014, Kruse and Koster again made contact with *Svalbardposten*. Both before and after their fieldwork, they were interviewed by Christopher Engås, resulting in the article ‘Marmoren kan ha skylden’ in Nr. 31 of August 8, 2014 (Appendix A7.3).

The author hopes to uphold the invaluable connection with *Svalbardposten* in order to inform the citizens of and visitors to the archipelago of the important and interesting interdisciplinary archaeological research that is going on in their backyard.

Workshop at the Svalbard Museum

“Marble at Fault” was a multi-phased project. The first phase was a workshop, which took place at the Svalbard Museum in Longyearbyen on Saturday, January 25, 2014. Kruse presented the results of her thesis with a particular focus on Marble Island to interested parties and potential interdisciplinary partners with the goal to raise public awareness of the issues at stake and enthusiasm for the project.

SEPF reporting requirements

“Marble at Fault” being primarily funded by the Svalbard Environmental Protection Fund, the project was subject to some additional reporting requirements. Further to this final fieldwork report, an audience-friendly report (Appendix 7.4) was written, the figures of which were also made into a short PowerPoint presentation (Appendix A7.5). That that project found repeated mention in *Svalbardposten* has been related above.

Archive location

All data relating to the research projects “Marble at Fault” and “Consequences of exploitation” are currently being held by Dr Frigga Kruse at the Arctic Centre of the University of Groningen. As far as possible, she will make use of the Research in Svalbard (RiS) database to share the data and disseminate the results of both projects. It is currently unknown if Askeladden, Norway’s database for cultural heritage, will be able to facilitate further archiving.

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On behalf of the interdisciplinary research team on Blomstrand,

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of several overlapping, fluid strokes that form a stylized, somewhat abstract shape.

Dr. Frigga Kruse

Polar historical archaeologist

Arctic Centre, University of Groningen

March 16, 2015

Appendix 1

GPR survey at the quarries

A1.1 GPR equipment in use

Due to a limit on the luggage that could be taken on the plane, the entire gear for two people had to be drastically reduced.

Only one antenna was used in the field instead of the usual range of three.

A1.2 Historical quarry and borehole locations on Blomstrand in 1920

'Sketch plan of Marble Island, Kings Bay, Spitsbergen' (slightly cropped). (Source: Northern Exploration Company file, Norwegian Polar Institute Archive, Tromsø.)

Extract of the above sketch plan. Marked in red are the features which guided the positioning of the GPR survey grids: No. 3 Quarry opened in summer 1912, two boreholes drilled in winter 1912/13, the Winter Quarry opened in winter 1919/20, and Quarry A13 (also referred to as the Lighthouse Quarry by the author) opened in spring 1920, (Source: NEC file, NPI, Tromsø.)

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

Summarised from the Day Book kept by David Booth, September 1912 - July 1913

Note:

There were two diamond corers. Mr Millar operated the second one; his day book has not yet been found. Furthermore, Leech (1920) reports that a party consisting of Manager, Mechanic, Cook, and eight men drilled 7 holes to various depths.

Borehole 1, location unknown [Millar cemented a hole] (58 ft 6 in = 17.83m)

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments	
Sep	23		Booth set up own machine, ready to start tomorrow	
	24		little headway, marble brittle	
	25		ground v. broken on surface	
	26	1 7	v. brittle, great trouble	
	27	2 6	brittle	
			seemed more solid, no cores, trouble getting water up to machine house [second machine cemented hole to prevent pebbles falling in]	
	28	3 0		
	30		pump burst, pumps frozen every morning	
	Oct	2	3 10	no solid cores yet
		3	4 6	trouble with broken pieces
4		5 2		
5		6 4	little better, 14" in 4 hours, longest piece 4"	
7		7 4	brought up sea water, doesn't freeze as quickly as fresh water	
8		8 6	no core yet	
9		9 6	1' today	
10		11 0	1'6", no solid cores yet	
11		12 0	1' today	
12		13 0	1' today, no solid core	
			[Booth setting diamonds for several days]	
21		13 6	1'6" today [sic], no long cores	
22		14 8	1'2" today, no solid cores	
23		15 8	1' today, same result	
24		16 8	1' today, got 9" core, longest yet	
25		17 11	1'3", getting better results	
26		18 6	7" today	
28		19 6	1', so brittle, broken pieces	
29	20 8	1'2", no better results		
30	22 2	1'6", same results		
31	23 5	1'3", no better		
Nov	1	25 2	1'9", same results	
	2	26 0	10", same results	
	4	26 10	10", great trouble, broken cores	
	5	28 8	1'10", still broken cores	
	6	30 2	1'6", same results	

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

	7	31	5	1'3", same results
	8	32	5	1'4" of dark, 8" of red and blue, still v. brittle
	9	33	2	same colour
	11	34	3	1'1" same stuff, no better
	12	35	9	1'6"
	13	37	0	1'3"
	14	38	8	1'8"
	15	40	2	1'6"
	16	41	0	10", seems better
	18	42	9	1'9", no better
	19	44	4	1'7"
	20	45	10	1'6", whiter grey
	21	47	6	1'8", looks good, no long cores
	22	49	6	2', same quality, no long cores
	23	50	6	1'
	26	52	0	1'6", 9" core
	27	54	7	2'7", 1' core, good, more solid
	28	55	7	1'
	29	57	0	1'5"
	30	57	10	10"
Dec	2	58	6	8", shifting machine due to ice

**Borehole 2, unknown location, cemented
(32 ft 5 in = 9.88m)**

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments
Dec	5		my men making hole for water'
	7	1 6	1'6", very brittle, 'can't expect anything better from surface'
	9	3 0	1'6"
	11	3 8	8"
	12	4 8	1'
	16	7 7	2' [sic], no solid cores
	17	9 7	2'
	18	11 3	1'8", broken cores
	19	13 1	1'10", no change in marble
	20	15 9	2'8", better today
	21	16 10	1'1", much better, no flaws
	23	18 0	1'2", still good looking
	24		cemented hole to stop loose stuff falling
	27		Been getting ice all day too cold for work with diamonds 35°C'
	28		Couldn't bore today 36°C'
	30		Getting ice from the holes of both places'
	31	19 0	1'
Jan	2	20 6	1'6", no long cores
	3	22 3	1'9", no better
	4	23 3	1'

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

6	24	6	1'3"
7	26	3	1'9"
8	27	11	1'8"
9	28	11	1'
10	29	11	1', slow progress, cores breaking
11	30	11	1'
13	32	5	1'6", lost diamond down hole, going to try shot boring

**Borehole 3, 'old Quarry place', at a height of 9.9m asl, cemented
(50 ft 1 inch = 15.27m)**

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments
Jan 15			shot boring no a success, hole not large enough, perhaps better with 3' 1/2" to get better results
16			removing machine house to 'old Quarry place' in the hope of getting some cores
17			setting up machine, getting house ready
18			ready for boring on Monday
20			bored 1' but earth, have to cement over as hot water makes it roll down hole
21			tried boring but have to cement over again as not hard enough, very hard to get cement to harden, it freezes first before drying
24	1	0	1'
25	2	0	1'
27	4	0	2'
28	8	6	4'6", no cores
30	11	6	3', v. brittle
31	13	0	1'6", no solid cores
Feb 1	14	0	1', 9 1/2" core
3	16	6	2'6", 9" core
4	20	0	3'6", seems more solid
5	22	4	2'4", not so good
6	25	1	2'9"
7	26	7	1'6", v. much broken
8	28	0	1'5", brittle
10	32	6	4'6", better now at sea level
12	36	6	2'0", not any better
13	38	6	2'0", very good
14	41	1	2'7", no better
17	42	1	1'
18	44	1	2', no better
20	46	1	2', marble v. bad
21	47	1	1', much worse
			[involved in the Schröder-Stranz relief expedition]
Mar 3	48	1	1', no hope for this hole
4	48	9	8", marble v. bad
5	49	7	10", no better

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

6 50 1 6", worst hole so far

**Borehole 4, on Millar's machine
abandoned**

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments
Mar 7	1	6	1'6"
10	1	6	had to shift Millar's machine, machine had no foundation and moved every time the core jammed

**Borehole 5, on Millar's machine, at shore
(50 ft = 15.24m)**

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments
Mar 11	1	3	1'3"
12	4	3	3'
13	6	9	2'6", no core larger than 3"
14	9	0	2'3", v. brittle
15			regulator had to be repaired
17	11	0	2', not any better
			3', seems better, would larger diameter of 4" or 5" get longer cores?
18	14	0	
19	14	6	6"
			1'6", 'as I suspected there was a nail down the hole I have no proof but I think some of the men must have dropped it down as I know for certain there were no nails near the hole yesterday or today'
20	16	0	
21	17	6	1'6", stuff all grinding itself up in hole
22	18	8	1'2"
25	20	8	2', marble no better
26	21	8	1', ground up
27	22	8	1', ground up
28	25	8	3', no cores, why?
29	27	2	1'6", same
30			[Millar returns]
31			[Booth leave for Cross Bay; coring continued by Millar?]
Apr 20	50	0	hole abandoned

**Borehole 6, 'went uphill again as place at shore not so good'
(71 ft 6 in = 21.79m)**

Date	Depth (total) feet & inches		Booth's comments
Apr 21			started to remove house, left shore and went uphill again

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

	22		still shifting house, very long way to drag sledge with machine, snow very deep just now
	23		house finished, machine set up, only water hole to get finished
	24		water hole finished
	25	0 8	8"
	26	1 8	1', no cores
	28	4 2	2'6", no cores
	29	6 2	2', no cores
	30	9 2	3', small cores
May	1	11 8	2'6", 2" - 3" cores
	2	13 8	2', same results
	3	15 2	1'6", small cores, breaks every 5 - 10 min
	5	17 2	2'
	6	19 8	2'6"
	7	22 8	3'
	8	26 0	3'4", only using one machine
	9	29 6	3'6"
	10	30 6	1', no better cores
	12	33 10	3'4", no large cores
	14	38 4	4'6", 6" core
	15	43 0	5', no large cores
	16	46 9	3'9", same results
	17	48 0	1'3"
	19	49 0	1'
	20	51 3	2'3"
	21	52 8	1'5"
	22	55 0	2'4", marble better, 8" cores
	23	58 0	3'8" [sic], more solid looking
	24	59 0	1'
	26	61 0	2', seemed much better quality
	27	63 8	2'8", no long cores yet
	28	66 5	2'9", 8" core
	29	70 1	3'6", 1 ft of clay at 67' down, then greyish marble
	30	71 6	1'5", ship came in the afternoon so no boring afterwards

			gave Simpson and Brackley light job of cleaning boring machines am
Jul	10		putting one machine in store
	11		finished cleaning machines put one in store
	23		[end of Day Book]

Following these geotechnical details, it is curious that Leech (1920) should report that 'many of the cores obtained were polished and sent to the London Office, and appear to be sound, attractive and good class marbles. I presume there is a report in the London Office by Mr. Miller, the Manager of this party, and this probably contains valuable information as to the quality and variety of marble at various depths. There is a report by Mr. Booth, the Mechanic, but this gives no detailed information of the marble at various depths.'

A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13

From David Booth's photo album:

David Booth.

Diamond coring, March 31, 1913. Booth second from left.

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

The following pages have been copied from Leech, H. W. (1920) *Report on various marble properties in Spitsbergen*, London: Northern Exploration Co. The full report is available in the Northern Exploration Co. file of the Norwegian Polar Institute Archive in Tromsø.

with red and yellow veining on a dark ground. The marble then dips and turns into a dark coloured shale. This quarry was abandoned, presumably owing to failure to get any marketable output, and I quite agree this was a right decision.

Dealing with the work done in No. 2 Quarry, the marble is of the "Brocatelle" variety and although it appears to be quite sound beyond the damaged area, I do not advise further working here, as the quantity above sea level is probably insufficient to prove remunerative and water trouble is to be anticipated below sea level so close to the shore. (The old quarry bore hole of the 1912-13 Winter Season is near this excavation).

1912. SUMMER SEASON.

In 1912 work was commenced at No. 3 Quarry on 1st June, and additional huts were erected (four large and two small) the building of which occupied the time and energies of all the men until August 17th, when the crane and machinery arrived (including two channelers of seven and ten tons respectively). The unloading and fixing of this machinery took several days and on the 8th September all machinery ceased work owing to frost. During this short period, however, good work must have been done, for a space 33 ft. wide was channeled at No. 3 Quarry, (Devonian Area, Bugtsten type), all within 500 yards of the camp, from a feather edge to a depth of 4ft. 6 ins. but only about one-eighth of this had been cut out and removed, the remainder being still in situ with the blocks channeled, but their base

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

still fixed to the virgin rock. This being surface rock, I found it quite unsuitable for the market.

Here I found the "strike" of the marble was some 20° different from the directions of the channeled cuts, which consequently do not follow the best markings of the marble, in addition to which, marble cut at such an angle is liable to break away, especially when slabbed. This will greatly diminish its marketable value.

I found records of trouble with the water supply for the work during the season, but am of opinion that this could be remedied, at any rate, as far as an ordinary summer season is concerned.

1912-1913 WINTER SEASON.

During this season, a party consisting of Manager, Mechanic, Cook and eight men, drilled 7 holes to various depths. Many of the cores obtained were polished and sent to the London Office, and appear to be sound, attractive and good class marbles.

I presume there is a report in the London Office by Mr. Miller, the Manager of this party, and this probably contains valuable information as to quality and variety of marble at various depths. There is a report by Mr. Booth, the Mechanic, but this gives no detailed information of the marble at various depths.

1913 SUMMER SEASON.

During the summer season of 1913 a large and commodious storehouse was erected. A heavy railway, five and a half foot gauge, was constructed from the crane to the quarry (of 1913

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

Season) with a junction branch to the storehouse. This railway is for the steam crane and heavy transport, its length being some 550 yards. Apparently no quarry work was done this season.
FROM 1914 - 1918.

Mr. Minard was engaged to go thoroughly over the Island, and I presume he has furnished a full report to the Company.

There does not appear to be any record of work done on Marble Island during these years, which cover the period of the War.

When Mr. Salisbury Jones visited the property with a party in the summer of 1918, he found that the camp building, the storehouse and machinery had been much damaged and a great deal of the material stolen.

1919 SUMMER SEASON.

As no caretakers were left by the 1918 Expedition, the condition of the camp was found to be considerably worse than when Mr. Salisbury Jones saw it; more damage had been done and all working tools stolen; in fact, the whole camp was in a very dilapidated condition. Work began this season on 13th July and consisted of (1) Taking an inventory of the missing parts of machinery, etc. (2) Putting the stores in some sort of order.

No quarrying was done owing to the lack of men and workable machinery and the absence of tools, until the arrival of the S/S Christoffer Ellingsen on 7th September. This period is covered by my report to the Company, October 1919.

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

1919-20 WINTER SEASON.

During the winter season 1919-20, Mr. Sant was in charge and the cables received from him reported that satisfactory progress was being made with the quarry work. His report of June 1920 covers the work done.

1920 PROGRAMME.

A definite programme based on the above cables for the expenditure of £25,000 to enable 1,000 tons of marble to be shipped this season, was approved before I left London. This allowed for 50 quarry-men exclusive of staff.

With 14 quarry-men and staff and a portion of the machinery, I left Aberdeen on 1st June, 1920.

Arriving at King's Bay on June 15th, I handed to Mr. Sant your letter of instruction, and the same evening, with Mr. Bevan inspected the winter's work.

DETAILS OF WINTER SEASON 1919-20.

We found a trench had been opened within 30 yards of No. 3 quarry, which had already been channeled for immediate development. Mr. Sant's trench was in precisely the same type of marble as the above, and, therefore, I cannot see that any good purpose was served by Mr. Sant's work here. The trench was flooded with snow water, which could have easily been kept drained.

Some 50 feet from the entrance to this winter quarry, the rock showed a fault about nine feet wide which cut right through the face. Owing to the water we were unable to examine the marble closely, but it did not appear a good marketable variety.

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

We next proceeded to Section 2 where we found a cut channeled by the "Broncho" 12 ft. by 2 ft. We did not consider that this site was placed so as to give the best representative marble of this type, but in view of the work already done, and the necessity of giving definite information this season, we considered it best to continue work at this spot.

The foregoing covers the whole of the visible development work accomplished since 27th September, 1919, which had shown no practical result up to my arrival on June 15th, 1920 and was fully dealt with in my report of July 13th, 1920 sent to the Company from Spitsbergen.

REASON FOR DISCONTINUING WORK ON 1919 - 20 WINTER QUARRY.

The following day I went with Mr. Sant, and he agreed that for production this season, the winter quarry would be quite useless, owing to the fact that the trench had been driven along a natural slip. This was visible on the surface and I could not understand why Mr. Sant had chosen this spot. Explosives had been used, and there did not exist a quarry floor or face, owing to the manner in which the rock had been shattered.

It would have been necessary to remove the rock on the left hand side to the bottom of the quarry trench (some fifteen feet) then to channel a cut some five feet on right hand side and end of trench to get beyond the area damaged by explosives - thus making a quarry face and floor.

The fault fifteen feet wide running through the present trench would all be waste. Until the above has been accomplished

this quarry will not be in a producing stage.

In my opinion, with No.3 quarry able to produce almost the same variety of marble some 50 feet away, when the quarry floor has been cleared and the channelers capable of work again, it would be a waste of time and money to continue with the winter quarry.

DETAILS OF SECTION 2A, QUARRY A13.

The proposed quarry in Section 2A (commenced before my arrival, by a 12 by 2 ft. channeled cut) was continued. An approximate area of 734 superficial yards, by 54 inches at the greatest depth was cleared, enabling the marble under the weathered crust to be examined.

The broken nature of the marble on the surface almost entirely disappeared, the fractures were closely cemented together and on testing with the hammer in situ rang soundly.

I regret to say, however, that other disturbing features appeared. This marble has a greyish blue ground with white bands running through; these bands are approximately 12 ins. wide interspersed with the greyish blue in places. Thus the grey is far too prominent to make it a valuable marble. However, this information regarding the soundness of the marble at slight depth under so shattered a surface, is a very reassuring factor.

As the strata dips at an angle of about 25° it would be far too expensive to cut out the white bands, and leave so large a proportion worthless. Besides the cost of extraction, it is by no means up to the samples of Norden Lys now in the London

Office, and I am very disappointed with it.

Also a series of beds of similar marble protruding through what is at present the quarry floor is a very disturbing feature.

The quarry floor runs practically in a line due south east to north west. The intruding layers run north and south. This would mean, in working the quarry, the break up of the whole quarry face, as far as good blocks are concerned, and would also lead to extensive waste.

MACHINE DRILL BORING - SECTION 2A.

In view of the above, the machine drill being in order, I commenced work in the same section to enable me to form an opinion of the lower strata underlying those exposed by the quarry excavation.

Although both 3 in. and 4 in. holes were drilled to a depth of 7 ft. each, the marble crumbled, and shewed that we had struck a fault not visible on the surface. This should not be taken as evidence of unsoundness of the marble at depth, but was due solely to a fault.

I decided, therefore, to temporarily abandon this area for the following reasons:-

- (1) Owing to shortage of water.
- (2) I wanted the drill to test the Cross Bay deposit of White Marble.
- (3) I felt it unwise to spend more time and work in this particular area, especially as No. 3 quarry should, if enough work be done there next season, give a

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

sufficient output for testing the marketable output of the whole of our Devonian Deposit.

The work was carried on as far as possible, with the available men and machinery until the arrival of your cable of 5th July, which stated that the balance of machinery could not be sent.

This necessitated a complete alteration of the above plans. The insufficiency of advanced preparatory work made the working of the "Fil Saws" impracticable, so that the special men sent up there to work these, were, of necessity, put on work at which they were less experienced and less efficient.

DETAILS OF NO. 3 QUARRY.

The men brought back from Breccia Island (when the quarry gang was reduced) then removed the benches of useless surface rock from No.3 quarry (which was channeled in 1912) in

- 16. -

order to make it ready for a fair start when further men and workable machinery should be available.

The quarry was all clear and ready for production when I left at the end of the season, and although the quarry had shown some faults, the marble appeared quite solid at the four feet depth attained. I think the next cut will give us marketable and representative blocks of the Devonian type of Spitsbergen Marbles.

This quarry is about 50 yards from the winter quarry of 1919-1920 and 250 yards from the camp. It shows the better marble of the two quarries and should be worked in preference, especially as the latter, after having been syphoned and pumped dry, is again flooded, and from the manner in which the excavation was done in the winter 1919-1920, will always be subject to this trouble, unless specially trenched for draining.

At the present date the market value of marble of this type, sold in England in block, is from £10 to £10.10.0., per ton.

This completes my report on the quarry work up to the present time.

CONCLUSIONS.

That the Marble in the Devonian Area is solid at approximately five feet. This area has been proved by cores obtained from Diamond Drilling, which have shown that it possesses many varieties of Marble, all of which are extensive.

The remaining areas on Marble Island and the Mainland have not been sounded to prove depth, but judging from surface indications and from the small amount of development work done, there is every reason to believe that, with the exception of the Laminated area (which appears too faulted to be of commercial interest) they are in every way superior to the marbles in the

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

Devonian Area and higher prices should be obtained for these varieties.

The White Marble deposits at Tinayre Bay should be further prospected, bored, trenched and developed, and if it is found to be free from schist at depth, arrangements should be made to work this deposit. The cost of obtaining marketable blocks, in my opinion, would not exceed that of the quarrying costs on Marble Island.

So far, very little development work has been done on the Company's marble properties, except in the Marble Island Devonian Area, and even here the work has never been run on a commercial basis. Therefore, the costs obtained this season are not a fair average on which to base future work.

I do not consider that we have yet sufficient data to justify an opinion on winter quarrying in Spitsbergen. In any case, it does not appear to be practicable for the first two years of working.

In my opinion, this property can be made a commercial proposition if sufficient capital is available to open out a number of quarries on the most systematic, economic and up-to-date lines, and if a suitable selling organisation for the product is found. There should also be sufficient reserve

A1.4 Summary of historical quarries and boreholes, 1920

capital to keep the various depots well stocked.

If the above conditions are fulfilled and if advantageous terms can be made with a London firm for storing, working and selling Spitsbergen Marbles, as I have been informed may be arranged, I consider that a net profit of at least $7\frac{1}{2}\%$ would be assured.

Yours faithfully,

Herbert W. Leach

December.1920.

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Appendix 2

Full photographic record

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund storehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u> 1 </u> of <u> 6 </u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030754	Tourists in Ny Alesund	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030764	The London houses. London 2 in the process of being restored, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030765	Mellageret in the foreground, Jernlageret in the background, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030766	Railway embankment, Mellageret, looking NE	
Digital	P1030767	Railway sleepers: are they the same size as those used on Marble Island? Scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030769	Sleepers at a railway junction, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030773	Sleepers at parallel railway lines, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030744	Longer-than-average sleeper, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030775	Sleepers on a railway line heading for Kongsfjorden, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030776	Longer sleepers and a junction ahead, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030777	Railway junction and shorter sleepers, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030778	Railway lines leading to Kongsfjorden, tracks remaining under narrow-gauge locomotive, from the internet: The surviving loco is no. 2, a 900mm gauge Borsig 0-4-0T, works number 7095 of 1909. It sits on a length of the old track next to the harbour with its train of old coal wagons, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030779	Locomotive on old 900mm tracks, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030780	Locomotive on old 900mm tracks, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030781	No. 2, a 900mm gauge Borsig 0-4-0T, works number 7095 of 1909, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030782	Locomotive and coal wagons, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030783	Coal wagon, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030784	View towards kayak store and pier, no signs of a railway terminal remain, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030785	Kayak store, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030787	Kayak store, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund warehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u>2</u> of <u>6</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030788	brick near the kayak store, 9135/144/K	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030789	Boat house, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030790	Boat house, rail tracks leading into the water, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P103792	Remains of a slipway in the water, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030794	Reused tracks from the boathouse to the water, not a standard broad gauge / broader than Indian and narrower than Brunel, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030795	Reused tracks from the boathouse to the water, not a standard broad gauge / broader than Indian and narrower than Brunel, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030796	Width of railway track, scale in cm	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030797	Jernlageret, north face and east face, scale 1m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030798	Jernlageret, east face, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030799	Imprints of railway sleepers towards (and along?) the north side of Jernlageret, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030800	Same line of imprints of sleepers heading eastwards towards Manevatnet, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030801	Wooden building or working platform to the east of Jernlageret, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030802	Wooden building or working platform to the east of Jernlageret, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030803	Jernlageret, east face and south face, scale 2m, looking NW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030804	Jernlageret, south face, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030805	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030806	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030807	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030808	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030809	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund storehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u>3</u> of <u>6</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030810	Wooden platform to the east of Jernlageret, signs of burning, colonisation of mosses, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030811	Jernlageret, south face, detail of window, scale (white) 50cm, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030812	Jernlageret, south face, detail of windows, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030813	Jernlageret, south face and west face, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030814	Jernlageret, west face, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030815	Jernlageret, west face, right (southern) door, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030816	Jernlageret, west face, central gate, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030817	Jernlageret, west face, left (northern) door and shed door, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030818	View of narrow-gauge locomotive and waggons from Jernlageret, looking NW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030819	Jernlageret, west face and north face, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030820	View of boat house from Jernlageret, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030821	Jernlageret, north face, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030823	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030824	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030825	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030826	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030827	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030828	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030829	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030830	Jernlageret, inside	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030831	View of 'London houses' and Zeppelinfjellet from Jernlageret, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund storehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u>4</u> of <u>6</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030823	How spray point on loose gravel disperses, scale (red) 50cm	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030837	Trapdoor fax trap on the way to the shooting range	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030840	Fox trap mechanism	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030841	A second fox trap	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030842	A third fox trap	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030843	A fourth fox trap?	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030857	Toilet with 'running water'	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030858	Toilet with 'running water'	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030861	Monument to Roald Amundsen	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030862	Monument to Amundsen, detail of the commissioners of the monument	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030863	Monument to Amundsen, use of marble	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030864	Monument to Amundsen, characteristics of the marble	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030865	Monument to Amundsen, characteristics of the marble	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030866	Monument to Amundsen, characteristics of the marble	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030870	Jernlageret, bricks: 'Höganäs' (Swedish), 'Borgestad 6-X', 'Borgestad 73C-811' (Norwegian)	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030871	Jernlageret, bricks: 'Borgestad 70D-811', 'Borgestad 70E-811' (Norwegian)	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030872	London 1, south face, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030873	London 1, south face and west face, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030874	London 1, west face, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030875	London 1, west face and north face, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030876	London 1, north face, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund storehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u>5</u> of <u>6</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030877	London 1, north face and east face, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030878	Former toilets between London 1 and London 2, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030879	Bucket in the former toilet	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030880	London 2 under renovation, west face and north face, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030881	London 2, north face, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030883	London 2, north face and east face, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030884	London 2, east face, scale 2m, looking NW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030885	London 2, east face and south face, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030886	London 2, north face (oblique view due to obstacle in the way of the photographer), scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030887	London 2, north face (oblique view due to obstacle in the way of the photographer), scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030888	Former toilets between London 1 and London 2 being used as storage, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030889	Carpenter's marks used in the renovation	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030890	Former toilets between London 1 and London 2 being used as storage, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030891	London 3, south face and west face, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030892	London 3, west face, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030893	London 3, west face and north face, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030894	London 3, north face, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030895	London 3, north face and east face, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030896	Former toilets between London 3 and London 4, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030897	London 4, north face and east face, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030898	London 4, east face, scale 2m, looking NW	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140711 - Ny Alesund storehouse and 'London houses'			Sheet <u>6</u> of <u>6</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030899	London 4, east face and south face, view obscured by modern toilet facilities, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030900	London 4, south face, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030901	Former toilets between London 3 and London 4 being used to house young goslings, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1030902	London 3, south face, looking NE	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1040906	Jernlageret, inside, the measurement are in inches	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1040907	Jernlageret, inside, the measurement are in inches	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1040908	Jernlageret, detail of window in north face	FK, 11/07/14
Digital	P1040909	Jernlageret, detail of window in south face	FK, 11/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140712 - Marble Island Reconnaissance			
			Sheet <u> 1 </u> of <u> 7 </u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030911	Benjamin Koster (BK) investigating the natural slip surface in the Winter Quarry (WQ), looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030912	At Quarry 3 (Q3): the metal may have been part of a crane; the boulders were used as weights on the crane; railway tracks in the back and the foundation (earthworks) of a crane just beyond, scale 2m, looking N	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030913	At Q3: the metal may have been part of a crane; boulders as weights, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030915	At Q3: foundations (earthworks) of a crane (compare to Camp Miller), scale 2m, looking N	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030916	Q3, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030918	At Q3: the rock outcrop Q3 had been sunk into, would the GPR survey show how competent the rock is?, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030920	At Q3: panorama of rock outcrop and spoil heap, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030923	At Q3: two boreholes, one with a wooden stake and one with a metal hook, historical or recent?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030925	At Q3: two boreholes with the mark B5-68, the mark refers to the fifth borehole drilled in 1968, it was started and finished on Thursday, August 8 (according to a calendar in Camp Mansfield)	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030928	At Q3: 'tool marks' of the channeler used to cut the marble, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030929	At Q3: 'tool marks' of the channeler used to cut the marble, scale 10cm, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030931	At Q3: 'tool marks' of the channeler used to cut the marble, scale 10cm, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030932	At Q3: 'an actor' investigated the streaks in the marble at this location, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030934	At Q3: close-up of the investigated streaks, the marks of a crowbar or pick are clearly visible, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030935	At Q3: close-up of the investigated streaks, the marks of a crowbar or pick are clearly visible, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030936	At Q3: close-up of the investigated streaks, the marks of a crowbar or pick are clearly visible, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030937	At Q3: east face of quarry, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030938	At Q3: east face of quarry, unworked outcrop beyond, scale 2m, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030939	At Q3: south face of quarry, scale 2m, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030940	At Q3: the channeled cut along the south face had been extended westwards, scale (white only) 50cm, looking W	FK, 12/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140712 - Marble Island Reconnaissance			
			Sheet <u>2</u> of <u>7</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030941	At Q3: close-up of the channeled cut along the south face to the west, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030942	At Q3: west face of quarry, natural cracks clearly visible, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030943	At Q3: west face of quarry, natural cracks clearly visible, unworked outcrop beyond, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030945	At Q3: west face of quarry, the rock between the face and a second channeled cut behind (barely visible) has crumbled, yet the rock beyond the second cut is still intact, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030946	At Q3: two channeled cuts made beyond the west face of the quarry but not exploited, the crumbled rock is clearly seen to affect one row but not the next, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030947	At Q3: close-up of a channeled cut, tool marks?, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030949	At WQ: close-up of brecciated marble, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030952	Near WQ: a small borehole, was its purpose sampling the rock or placing a shot; borehole B2-68 (finished on Tuesday, July 30) in the background	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030953	Near WQ: close-up of the same drill hole, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030954	Near WQ: another small drill hole, borehole B2-68 in the back	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030955	Near WQ: close-up of the same drill hole, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030956	Near WQ: a third drill hole, all lie in line with the west face of the winter quarry, so blasting seems an option, looking N	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030958	WQ: the west face of the winter quarry exposes a large fault running NW-wards, the fault surfaces reach the surface and are clearly visible there, BK is investigating the natural slip surface, scale 2m, looking NW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030961	WQ: the large fault in the winter quarry, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030962	WQ: the fault surface (fault throw, fault scarp) visible on the surface, looking NW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030965	WQ: the large fault in the west face of the winter quarry appears to change direction towards the SE, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030967	WQ: natural slip surface (right) and marble disturbed by faulting (centre and left), looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030970	Above WQ: characteristics of the marble: streaks of quartz (?) being weathered out of the outcrop, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030971	Above WQ: close-up of the streaks of quartz (?), scale (white only) 50cm	FK, 12/07/14

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1030972	Above WQ: B1-68 (finished Saturday, July 27), again a hole and a metal hook, to secure the rig in wind maybe?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030974	Above WQ: close-up of the borehole, remarkably intact edges! Despite the crack through it and nearby hole	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030975	Above WQ: close-up of the borehole, diameter ca. 65mm, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030976	Above WQ: borehole blocked by fallen gravel (not ice), max. depth not known	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030977	Above WQ: borehole blocked by fallen gravel (not ice), max. depth not known	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030979	A 'compound hole', why drill the same hole three times?!	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030980	Rock edges and broken rock: natural or an exploration feature?, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030981	Borehole B1-b-68 (finished Wednesday, July 31) plus metal hook, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030982	Same borehole and metal hook	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030985	BK at a local triangulation station (trig point) 37mOD, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030986	The actual trig point 'Statens Kartverk 1995' 37mOD	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030988	Panorama of Peirsonhamna, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030990	View over railway embankment towards Ny Alesund, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030991	View over building and crane towards Peirsonhamna, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030992	Impressive vein on south coast to the west of Peirsonhamna, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030994	Questionable remains on south coast west of Peirsonhamna, fox trap?, beacon?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030995	Impressive vein on south coast to the west of Peirsonhamna, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1030998	Impressive vein, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040001	Impressive vein	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040003	Impressive vein, scale, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040004	Impressive vein, scale 2m, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14

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Digital	P1040005	BK taking photographs of the vein, scale 2m, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040007	Impressive vein, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040009	Impressive vein, scale (red only) 50cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040011	Impressive vein, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040013	Recent crack between vein and Peirsonhamna, scale 2m, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040014	Close-up of recent crack, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040015	Close-up of recent crack, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040017	Close-up of recent crack, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040018	BK taking photographs of recent crack between vein and Peirsonhamna, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040021	A fault zone (?) immediately to the west of Peirsonhamna, looking SW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040024	A fault zone (?) immediately to the west of Peirsonhamna, scale 2m, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040028	Panorama taken from western corner of Peirsonhamna into the natural harbour, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040030	Location of a former crane of winch (?) at the former fishery station, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040031	Close-up of the location of a former crane, wire ropes, what is the dark stuff?, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040032	Below the location of the crane: the water of Peirsonhamna, is there any underwater archaeology?, could the divers see anything?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040033	Small bay and beach on west side of Peirsonhamna, could this have been a quarry?. Looking N	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040034	Small quarry (for building stone?) and spoil heap at the end of the railway embankment, looking W	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040038	Small quarry (for building stone?) and spoil heap at the end of the railway embankment, looking N	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040039	Quarried block, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040040	Quarried block, scale (red only) >50cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040041	Block split by wedging / plug-and-feather? But the holes are too far apart... scale (white only) 50cm	FK, 12/07/14

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Digital	P1040042	Drill hole in quarried block, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040044	Line of drill holes (closer together this time), wedging / plug-and-feather method	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040045	Piece of wood among the quarried blocks	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040047	Brecciated marble	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040048	A large block, which method?, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040049	A metal plug: plug-and-feather method	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040050	Plugs and a feather: plug-and-feather method	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040051	Different size blocks of marble, scale 2m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040052	A borehole in a quarried block of marble: from 1912/13?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040053	A borehole in a quarried block of marble: from 1912/13?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040055	A borehole in a quarried block of marble: from 1912/13?	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040056	End of the railway embankment on the west side of Peirsonhamna, marble blocks for construction, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040057	Borehole with concrete cover near railway embankment: 1912/13!, scale 1m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040058	Cinder and burnt rock (?) near borehole near railway embankment, scale 1m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040059	Cinder and burnt rock (?) near borehole near railway embankment	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040060	Cinder, burnt rock, metal/nails	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040061	Straps of metal	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040062	Flakes of metal, scale >50cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040063	Piece of metal as if shaped around borehole, scale >50cm	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040064	Close-up of borehole with concrete cover and remnants of metal	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040066	Close-up of borehole with concrete and metal, scale 10cm	FK, 12/07/14

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Digital	P1040067	View along a line of gravel patches towards the 1912/13 borehole, which could have suggested a line of weakness (unless borehole was placed in snow...), looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040068	View along a small crack and gravel patches towards the 1912/13 borehole, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040069	Borehole along line of vision in two previous photographs, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040070	Borehole in line with further gravel patches, possible line of weakness, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040071	Borehole in line with further gravel patches, possible line of weakness, looking SE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040072	Railway embankment coming from the crane (top right), note construction pit centre left, scale (white only) 50cm, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040073	Where the railway embankment would have gone if the line had been kept: the previously mentioned fault zone at the shore, which may have made for a good little landing point, looking S	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040075	Modern cup-marked stone near building ruin: probably someone being very bored, scale 1m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040076	Rock edge and gravel near crane: an exploration site?, scale 1m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040077	Ore bucket at the crane: rocks probably placed by tourists	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040078	Rock edge beneath the crane: quarried or straightened?, scale 1m	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040080	Livellazione Istituto Idrografico xxMarina Italiana Genova 1928 - Anno VI'	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040081	Metal ring near the crane	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040082	Water of Peirsonhamna beneath the crane	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040083	Water of Peirsonhamna from the crane, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040084	Water of Peirsonhamna from the crane, looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040085	Calendar from 1968 in Camp Mansfield: it lists the boreholes drilled that year!	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040086	Calendar from 1968 in Camp Mansfield: it lists the boreholes drilled that year!	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040916	Aerial view of Blomstrand, Marble Island, looking NW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040917	Aerial view of Blomstrand, Marble Island, looking N	FK, 12/07/14

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Digital	P1040918	Aerial view of Blomstrand, Marble Island, looking NW	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040919	Aerial view of the Lovenoyane, Conwaybreen in the back, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040920	Aerial view of the Lovenoyane, Conwaybreen in the back, looking NE	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040921	Aerial view of Kongsbreen (left), Colletthogda (centre), and Kronebreen (right), looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040922	Aerial view of Kongsbreen (left), Colletthogda (centre), and Kronebreen (right), looking E	FK, 12/07/14
Digital	P1040923	Aerial view of Revneset into Hanaskogdalen, looking E	FK, 12/07/14

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Digital	P1040089	Benjamin Koster (BK) setting up GPR equipment near Grid 1, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040090	BK setting up GPR equipment, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040091	Grid 1 immediately west of the winter quarry (WQ), corner 1B, WQ/workshop/crane in the background, looking NE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040093	Grid 1, corner 1D coincides with borehole B1-68, looking towards corner 1B, scale, 1m, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040095	Grid 1 immediately west of WQ, how would the fault show up?, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040097	Grid 1, BK indicating the direction of a fault surface as evident on the surface, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040100	Grid 1, immediately west of WQ, the presence and direction of a large fault are visible at the surface, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040101	Remains of a smithy? Earthworks (foundations), corrugated galvanised iron (corrugated iron or CGI), bricks, cinder, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040102	Remnant of a stove used at the smithy: Columbian Stoveworks	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040103	Remains of a smithy? Earthworks, corrugated iron, bricks, cinder, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040105	Remains of a smithy?, scale 1m, looking NE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040108	Smithy, construction detail: corner of a building or shed, scale 1m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040109	Smithy, construction detail: corner of a building or shed, interesting vegetation patches, scale 1m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040110	Barrel next to workshop, scale 1m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040111	Barrel next to workshop	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040112	Drilling equipment in workshop	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040113	Fractures running NW to SE, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040115	Panorama of marble outcrop, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040118	BK and GPR survey in progress in Grid 1, varied topography and varied surface (solid vs gravel), looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040121	BK and GPR survey in progress in Grid 1, varied topography and varied surface (solid vs gravel)	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040125	BK and GPR survey in progress in Grid 1	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040127	BK and GPR survey in progress in Grid 1, fault scarp?, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040136	Tourists at the quarries, most did not see Q3, none came up to ask what we were doing, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040141	Marble outcrop, could this be an anthropogenic edge?, gun for scale	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040142	Marble outcrop, could this be an anthropogenic edge?, the gravel is roughly of the same size but then there is a cobble	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040143	Marble outcrop, colour changes indicate fresh damage, note the drill hole in the centre, gun for scale	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040145	Close-up of the drill hole	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040152	Gully leading towards the fishery station, could this be a fault?, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040153	Panorama of marble outcrop and Peirsonhamna, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040159	Fresh rock, damage caused by drill holes	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040160	Fresh rock and drill hole	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040161	Piece of cloth, was it important in the drilling process?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040621	View from the marble outcrop along a water pipe (centre left), looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040163	Following the water pipe to its source, BK standing next to imprint of pipe in former location, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040166	Looking back along the water pipe towards the quarries/workshop/crane, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040167	Along the course of the water pipe, has digging or blasting taken place here?, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040168	Along the course of the water pipe, has digging or blasting taken place here?, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040169	The water pipe, a larger pipe from the source become a smaller pipe towards the quarries	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040170	The water pipe in / next to a stream, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040171	Pieces of wood, planks in the stream	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040172	The metal pipe has been split over time	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040173	Water still runs in the split pipe	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040174	Water pipe near the source of the water, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1041075	End of the water pipe disappearing under sediment (bottom centre), wooden planks ahead: remains of a small dam?, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040176	Wooden planks and beams sticking out of the sediment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040177	More wooden planks, yet any structure no longer recognisable, was there a pump?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040178	The source of the water in the water pipe that fed the quarries	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040179	Fairly long wooden planks	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040181	Anthropogenic damage to the rock outcrop?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040182	Water flowing over the rock outcrop, water source for the quarries	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040183	Water flowing over the rock outcrop, water source for the quarries, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040185	View over Peirsonhamna, a fault line? looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040187	Panorama over Peirsonhamna and Kongsfjord, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040188	View towards the quarries and the marble outcrop, Ny Alesund in the background, looking SW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040189	View of Peirsonhamna, the quarries and the marble outcrop, Ny Alesund in the background, Looking SW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040191	View in the direction of Peirsonhamna, 'path of least resistance' (centre), what features in the landscape determine the formation of a path?, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040192	Wooden remains, a bear or fox trap?, reindeer bones	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040193	Wooden remains, a bear or fox trap?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040196	Footpath onto the escarpment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040198	Obvious fractures on the escarpment above Peirsonhamna, gun for direction and scale, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040199	The escarpment above Peirsonhamna, a fault? Not our remit to answer that question, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040205	View from the escarpment over Peirsonhamna, where would the faults run?, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040206	View from the escarpment over the quarries and the marble outcrop, looking SW	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040207	View from the escarpment to discern the course of the stream, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040208	The rock between which the stream flows onto the plain, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040211	Point where the stream leaves the escarpment, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040212	Installations, probably scientific, at the stream edge on the escarpment, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040213	Installations, probably scientific, where the stream leaves the escarpment, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040214	Water spreads over the plain, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040215	A water pipe lies in a gully that has long since dried up, the water has found a different route (unless at times of snow melt?), looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040216	Claim sign (SNSK) at the bottom of the escarpment, who would have seen it here? Or were there workings?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040217	Part of a drilling rig having been rolled into the stream	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040218	Part of a drilling rig having been rolled into the stream	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040219	Part of a drilling rig having been rolled into the stream	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040221	Vegetation enclosure erected by Maarten Loonen, near the former storehouse	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040222	Equipment, the intention is to have a 'database' to compare to machines used in historical photographs	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040223	Series of events: rail under burnt floor under new rail, in storehouse	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040224	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040225	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040226	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040227	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040228	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040229	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040230	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040231	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040232	Equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040233	Drilling rods among equipment	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040234	Detail of drilling rod, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040235	Vegetation exclosure erected by Maarten Loonen, near the former storehouse	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040237	Former storehouse, now focal point of equipment, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040238	Former storehouse, now focal point of equipment, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040239	Sunken barrel, purpose unknown, water pipe beyond	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040240	Collection of door or window pane/shutter hinges	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040244	Former storehouse, note the differential soil erosion on either side, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040245	View from the storehouse to the quarries and the outcrop, why did the railway not lead across here?, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040246	Two craters made by blasting, vegetation using shelter/water?, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040247	Two craters made by blasting, vegetation using shelter/water?, gun for scale, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040249	Crater made by blasting, vegetation using shelter/water?, gun for scale, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040250	Trapdoor fox trap	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040252	View from the fox trap to the buildings, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040253	Second fox trap	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040254	Scatter of dynamite near fox traps	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040255	Dynamite, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040259	Dynamite	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040261	Dynamite, sawdust or some other absorbent material soaked in nitroglycerin plus protective coating	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040262	Dynamite	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040263	Location of dynamite in foreground in relation to two fox traps, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040264	Location of dynamite in foreground in relation to two fox traps, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040265	Dynamite, on a granite cobble, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040269	Dynamite	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040270	Dynamite with wrapping paper	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040272	Dynamite storage shed made of granite blocks (imported!), corrugated iron, a wooden door, signs of burning - did it explode?!, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040273	Wooden plank, weathered writing or weathered burning?, from a dynamite storage box? Or other warning?, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040274	Reverse of wooden plank, no writing or burning, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040276	Dynamite storage shed, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040277	Dynamite storage shed, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040278	Dynamite storage shed, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040279	Dynamite storage shed, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040280	Dynamite storage shed: a roughly hewn granite block (imported), scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040281	Dynamite storage shed: granite block, scale 10cm	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040282	Dynamite storage shed: use of cement, gun for scale	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040283	Dynamite storage shed: wooden planks, a storage box?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040285	Dynamite storage shed, more wooden planks, no signs of burning	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040286	Dynamite with partial brand name 'KYA... Trademark London' and A F	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040288	Dynamite, on granite block split by plug-and-feather	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040289	Dynamite storage box, some cloth, some burning	FK, 13/07/14

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040290	Dynamite storage shed: wooden door post, burnt	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040291	Dynamite storage shed: wooden door post, burnt	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040295	Dynamite storage shed, roughly hewn granite, drill hole	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040296	Dynamite storage shed: BK lifting CGI roof, exposing signs of burning	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040297	More dynamite	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040302	Close-up: ?EL?ONITE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040304	Close-up: KYN?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040308	Grid 2, corner 2B, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040309	Grid 2, view from corner 2B to corner 2A, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040310	Grid 2, view from corner 2A to corner 2B, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040311	Grid 2, view from corner 2C diagonally to corner 2B (corner 2A off to the right), looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040318	Unexpected bird's nest in the shelter of a boulder (Eider duck?) at the bottom of Grid 2	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040319	Feature of the marble, erosion by melt water or rain water	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040321	Feature of the marble, erosion by melt water or rain water	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040323	Features of the marble erosion by water and more resistant streaks (of quartz?)	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040329	Panorama of Peirsonhamna, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040334	Overview of Peirsonhamna beach, looking NW	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040340	Wooden stake on headland east of Peirsonhamna, unknown function	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040341	Survey point on headland east of Peirsonhamna, looking N	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040342	Survey point made of bricks and concrete, loose bricks, loose boulders, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040343	Survey point made of bricks and concrete, loose bricks, loose boulders, a trapdoor fox trap, looking NE	FK, 13/07/14

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040352	Metal rods on headland east of Peirsonhamna, a radio antenna?, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040353	Metal rods on headland east of Peirsonhamna, a radio antenna?, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040354	Metal rods on headland east of Peirsonhamna, a radio antenna?, reused water pipes? looking NE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040355	Close-up of metal rod	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040356	Footpath in the snow, is the 'dirt' from boots or blown in?, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040357	Footpath in the snow, is the 'dirt' from boots or blown in?, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040360	View towards the Lovenoyane, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040363	View along the SE coast of Marble Island towards Conwaybreen, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040367	Wooden planks and boulders, fox trap?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040368	View of Peirsonhamna beach, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040369	East end of beach, selected for metal detection, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040370	Result of metal detection: each yellow flag is a signal, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040371	Where do all the signal (the metal) come from: refuse being dropped from above?	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040373	Result of metal detection: each yellow flag is a signal, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040374	Result of metal detection, looking SE	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040375	Testing the method: metal rail visible at the surface traced using wooden toothpicks, the join-the-dots	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040376	Close-up of detection method using wooden toothpicks	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040377	Close-up of detection method using wooden toothpicks, metal rail centre left	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040378	Part of metal rail visible at the surface	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040379	Metal rail covered by beach sediments	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040381	Full extent of metal rail traced	FK, 13/07/14

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Digital	P1040382	Base of tub in beach sediments, scale 1m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040383	Base of tub in beach sediments, scale 1.5m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040384	Base of tub in beach sediments, approximate position of fourth wheel, scale 1.5m	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040385	Metal rails partially in beach sediments, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040386	Metal rails partially in beach sediments, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040388	Cave in west corner of beach	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040389	Cave in west corner of beach	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040390	Cave in west corner of beach	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040391	View out the window of Camp Mansfield, looking S	FK, 13/07/14
Digital	P1040392	View out the window of Camp Mansfield, looking S	FK, 13/07/14

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140714 - Marble Island Day 2			Sheet <u> 1 </u> of <u> 3 </u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040401	Panorama of unfinished railway embankment, looking SW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040403	Railway embankment in relation to Grid 3, Benjamin Koster (BK) at corner 3A, looking SW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040404	Grid 3, corner 3A, looking diagonally across to corner 3D, 3B to the left (not visible) and 3C to the right (just off), looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040406	Construction pit next to railway embankment, looking N	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040407	Construction pit next to railway embankment, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040408	Construction pit, looking N	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040409	Constructions pit, looking SW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040414	Small 'bay' in which the railway could have terminated, was it suited as a harbour?, no artefacts in the water	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040416	Small 'bay' at low tide, has it been quarried?, looking SE	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040417	Small 'bay' at low tide, has it been quarried?, looking SE	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040428	Dynamite, red, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040431	Early veins and later fractures, infilled, in the marble, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040435	Brecciated marble, gun for scale, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040436	Brecciated marble, gun for scale, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040438	Water in Peirsonhamna clearing up, looking E	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040440	Water in Peirsonhamna clearing up, looking E	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040441	Recent damage to the historical site?, metal peg of the radio antenna taken out of the ground	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040442	Location of the radio antenna, four anchors, looking S	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040443	Spoil of the Winter Quarry (WQ), different phases of dumping?, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040445	Relation of Quarry 3 (Q3, channeled groves in bottom right) to the spoil of WQ: commencing work at Q3 would run into problems with the spoil, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040446	Detail of metal rods that held the rails together, including nuts and bolts	FK, 14/07/14

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Digital	P1040447	A length of track being the reason why Grid 4 had to be place several meters to the W of Q3, looking S	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040451	Grid 4, corner 4C, 4A to the left, 4B diagonally across, 4D to the right, looking S	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040453	Grid 4, looking N	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040454	Grid 4, looking N	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040455	Overview: Q3, piece of track, Grid 4 beyond, WQ spoil in the background, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040456	Grid 4, looking S	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040459	Unmarked borehole (diagonally left off centre, scale 10cm), piece of track, earthwork foundations of stationary crane with boulders for weight, GPR antenna still at Grid 4, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040460	Unmarked borehole, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040461	Unmarked borehole, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040463	Unmarked borehole, was this drilled in 1912/13?	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040464	Drill hole in line of vision with borehole B5-68 and WQ spoil, western extent of Grid 5	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040466	Q3 and continuation of outcrop under investigation in Grid 5, looking E	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040467	Q3 and Grid 5, BK next to unmarked borehole / corner 5B, looking E	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040468	Grid 5: corner 5B, looking NE	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040469	Grid 5, corner 5D, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040470	Extent of outcrop to the east of Q3, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040471	Refuse immediately east of the upstanding buildings, how much of this is really archaeology?, looking NE	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040472	Remains of a British-built stove: 'Smith & Wellstood Ld Bonnybridge' (Falkirk, Scotland)	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040474	A brick 'Borgestad ???'	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040475	A cut bone, remains of the NEC cows?	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040476	A cut bone, remains of the NEC cows?	FK, 14/07/14

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Digital	P1040477	More dynamite at a house foundation, scale 10cm, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040478	More dynamite at a house foundation, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040479	A carbon rod of a battery	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040480	The remains of a battery, scale 10cm	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040481	Overview of settlement at Peirsonhamna, stream in foreground, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040482	Overview of settlement at Peirsonhamna, stream and beach, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040483	Headland to the east of Peirsonhamna, looking S	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040487	Settlement as seen from the headland, looking NW	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040488	Settlement as seen from the headland, looking W	FK, 14/07/14
Digital	P1040489	Remains of a British-built stove: 'Columbian Stove Works' (taken over by Smith & Wellstood Ld Bonnybridge, Falkirk, Scotland)	FK, 14/07/14

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Digital	P1040496	View of Marble Island from Ny Alesund, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040508	Glacier ice (Kongsbreen, Conwaybreen) in Kongsfjord, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040509	Glacier ice in Kongsfjord, Tre Kroner in the background, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040511	Norwegian fishing station in Peirsonhamna, looking W	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040512	Stationary crane in Peirsonhamna, looking NW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040514	Arriving on Marble Island in calm weather, Looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040516	Marble blocks at the Winter Quarry (WQ), looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040517	Marble blocks at the Winter Quarry (WQ), looking W	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040523	View of Peirsonhamna and Kongsfjord, Zeppelinfjellet in the centre, looking	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040524	Looking out for evidence of exploration, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040526	Trapdoor fox trap, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040531	View of marble outcrop and quarries (centre), Peirsonhamna, Kongsfjorden, Zeppelinfjellet (left), Broggerbraene (centre), Scheteligfjellet (right), did the boulders have a purpose?, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040543	Snow field on Blomstrand, Tre Kroner in the background, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040546	Fox trap?, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040547	Blomstrandhamna, Vestneset, Nordvagfjellet, looking NW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040551	Anthropogenic?, under Irgensfjellet, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040553	View from Irgensfjellet over Breneset towards the receding Blomstrandbreen, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040554	View from Irgensfjellet over Gerdoya towards Conwaybreen (left) and Kongsbreen (right), Irgenstjorna centre left, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040562	Small cairn on Irgensfjellet, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040570	On the descend, Breneset and Blomstrandbreen, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040573	Geocache location on Breneset (moraine, erratic)	FK, 15/07/14

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Digital	P1040574	Poorly tidied fire at geoache location at Breneset	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040579	Driftwood in Sorvagen, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040580	Driftwood in Sorvagen, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040581	Driftwood in Sorvagen, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040587	Bird cliffs under Irgensfjellet, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040590	Tightly folded rock, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040591	Looking back along Sorvagen towards Irgensfjellet, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040595	Folded rock on route to Hansneset, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040596	Hansneset, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040597	Shade!, is that washout or spoil?, looking W	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040599	Glacially polished rock surface, looking S	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040600	Grotteveggen, a fault scarp?, looking S	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040601	Grotteveggen, faulting?, looking E, looking S	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040602	Grotteveggen, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040604	Grotteveggen, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040605	Fox trap, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040607	View along west coast of Marble Island, lighthouse at Grottevika in the centre, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040608	Fox trap, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040609	Fox trap, cobble and nails but no wood	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040610	Fox trap 'in the landscape'	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040611	Fox trap	FK, 15/07/14

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Digital	P1040612	Fox trap	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040613	As above, with mechanism	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040615	Fox trap mechanism	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040616	Spoil of the Lighthouse Quarry (LQ), looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040618	Distance between quarry and Grottevika / lighthouse approx. 290m, looking NW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040619	Shore at LQ, view towards Ny Alesund, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040620	Two metal pegs at LQ, scale 1m, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040621	Two metal pegs and sinkhole at LQ, scale 1m, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040622	Rocks at the coast at almost high tide, would boating / shipping have been possible?, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040623	Coast at almost high tide, would boating / shipping have been possible?, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040624	Sinkhole and two metal pegs at LQ	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040625	Coast at almost high tide, would boating / shipping have been possible?	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040626	Cliff at LQ, looking W	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040627	LQ spoil as seen from the shore, hiding the quarry, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040628	LQ spoil, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040629	LQ spoil, some corrugated iron, scale 1m, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040630	Rock outcrop at LQ, does not look that broken up, scale 1m, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040631	LQ spoil and quarry, scale 1m, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040632	LQ, north corner and west face, scale 1m, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040633	LQ, scale 1m, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040634	LQ: piece of copper pipe, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14

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Digital	P1040635	LQ, scale 1m, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040636	LQ, method of working on the north face, series of close and deep drill holes, why?	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040637	LQ, method of working on the north face, rock along the edge somewhat broken up	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040638	LQ, north face, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040639	LQ, north face and east corner, scale 1m, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040640	LQ, west face, north corner, and north face, scale 1m, looking NW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040641	LQ, north face, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040642	LQ, north face	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040643	LQ, north face	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040644	LQ, north face, detail of drill hole, some clay	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040645	LQ, north face, line of drill holes, ranging rod marks another drill hole, scale >1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040646	LQ, north face, line of drill holes, another drill hole centre bottom	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040647	LQ, north face, ranging rod marks location of last drill hole in line, to its left the drill hole out of line, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040648	LQ, plant seeking shelter in drill hole	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040649	LQ, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040650	LQ, marble in quarry	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040651	LQ, west face, what was the method?, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040652	LQ, a drill hole in SW corner	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040653	LQ, a drill hole in SW corner	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040654	LQ, a drill hole on the west face	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040655	LQ, west face, approx. distance between drill hole in SW corner (left) and drill hole on west face, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 15/07/14

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Digital	P1040657	LQ, details of the west face, why is the quarry floor not straight?, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040658	LQ, drill hole in the NW corner	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040659	LQ, view of the outcrop, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040660	Fox traps, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040661	LQ, cinder?, scale 1m, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040662	LQ, length of rope, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040663	LQ, piece of quartz or calcite?, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040664	LQ, cinder or clinker?, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040665	LQ, diggin?, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040666	LQ, view of the outcrop, looking NE	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040667	LQ, view of the outcrop and other bits and pieces, looking E	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040669	LQ, fox trap	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040670	LQ, fox trap mechanism	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040671	LQ, two boreholes, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040672	LQ, two boreholes, scale 1m	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040673	LQ, two boreholes	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040674	LQ, two boreholes, scale in cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040675	LQ, smaller borehole, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040676	LQ, large borehole, scale 10cm	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040677	LQ, boreholes (again blocked by cobble) in line with LQ (and Zeppelinfjellet) fox trap to the left, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040678	LQ, natural or anthropogenic?, scale 1m, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14

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140712 - Marble Island Long Hike

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040679	Marble outcrop, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040680	Fox trap mechanism	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040681	Fox trap, looking SW	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040682	Fox trap	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040683	Fox trap mechanism	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040684	Fox trap	FK, 15/07/14
Digital	P1040686	View towards marble outcrop and quarries, looking SE	FK, 15/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140716 - Marble Island Lighthouse Quarry			Sheet <u> 1 </u> of <u> 3 </u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040690	Drain in the settlement that could be of interest for vegetation studies, scale 1m	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040692	Small beach to the east of Peirsonhamna, chosen to test metal detector, looking SE	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040693	Plastic find on beach	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040694	East end of beach, metal detection methodology: perpendicular to water line	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040695	East end of beach, metal detection methodology: perpendicular to water line	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040696	Organic find (apple) on beach	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040697	Change in methodology, starting along water line and surveying parallel to it --> maximisation in case of incoming tide	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040698	Organic find (orange peel) on beach	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040699	Organic find (second orange peel) on beach	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040700	Survey completed, our signals in total: two to the left and two by the rocks	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040702	Survey completed, our signals in total: two by the rocks	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040703	Anthropogenic find on beach, packing material?	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040704	Two signal caused by two nails in recent drift wood, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040705	Two signal caused by two nails in recent drift wood, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040707	A signal caused by an empty bullet shell, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040708	Plastic find (shotgun shell case) on beach	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040709	Empty bullet shell, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040710	Beach meets tundra, looking SW	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040711	Beach meets tundra, looking W	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040713	Lighthouse Quarry (LQ): boulder at shore and spoil just visible in the centre, looking W	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040714	LQ, Grid 6, corner 6A, 6C to the left, 6B to the right, looking NW	FK, 16/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140716 - Marble Island Lighthouse Quarry			Sheet <u>2</u> of <u>3</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040715	LQ, Grid 6, corner 6B, 6A to the left, 6D to the right, looking SW	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040716	Marble outcrop, scale 1m	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040717	Marble outcrop, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040718	Marble outcrop, scale 1m	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040719	Smaller borehole, total depth or blocked at 1.99m	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040720	Two boreholes next to each other - and the bridge did not crumble, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040721	Two boreholes next to each other - and the bridge did not crumble, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040722	Two boreholes next to each other - and the bridge did not crumble, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040724	LQ in better light than the evening before, looking W	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040726	LQ, west face, looking W	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040727	LQ, north face, looking N	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040728	LQ, close-up of west face, what method was used?, wire-saw?, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040729	LQ, close-up of west face, wire-saw? but highly uneven, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040730	LQ, close-up of west face, small percussion holes?, scale in cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040731	LQ, west face, scale 60cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040732	LQ, close-up of drill holes in north face, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040733	LQ, close-up of drill holes in north face, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040734	LQ, north face	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040735	LQ, north face, each hole was measured, scale 95cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040736	LQ, north face, each hole was measured, scale 95cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040737	LQ, north face, the holes veer off-course	FK, 16/07/14

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140716 - Marble Island Lighthouse Quarry			Sheet <u>3</u> of <u>3</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	P1040738	LQ, north face, drilling discontinued because a fracture was hit at this point	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040739	LQ, north face, plant marks intersection of fracture and line of holes	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040740	LQ, north face, fracture surface clearly visible, looking E	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040741	LQ, north face, fracture surface clearly visible, looking E	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040742	LQ, north face, fracture surface not so obvious when looking at it straight on, looking NE	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040743	LQ, north face, fracture surface not so obvious when looking at it straight on, looking NE	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040745	LQ, north face, line of drill holes terminated where fracture comes in, looking NE	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040746	LQ, north face, line of drill holes terminated where fracture comes in, looking NE	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040747	LQ, scale perpendicular to intended line of drilling, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040748	LQ, scale perpendicular to fracture, scale 1m, looking NW	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040750	LQ, north face, intersection of line of drilling and fracture from above	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040753	Maarten Loonen (ML) demonstrating splitting rock using soaked wood and letting it freeze - did this happen on Spitsbergen?	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040756	LQ, north face, diameter of holes difficult to measure, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040755	LQ, north face, diameter of holes difficult to measure, scale 10cm	FK, 16/07/14
Digital	P1040758	LQ as seen from the water, not the most inviting to boats	FK, 16/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140720 - Marble Island Walkover			Sheet <u> 1 </u> of <u> 4 </u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	DSC00779	Recent signs of reindeer about buildings on Marble Island	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00781	Name board 'Camp Smith', scale 1m	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00782	Name board 'Camp Smith', scale 1m	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00783	Name board 'Camp Smith', detail of nails, scale 30cm	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00784	Foundation of barrack entrance (feature 2d in Kruse, 2013), scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00785	Entrance 2d, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00786	Entrance 2d, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00787	Entrance 2d, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00788	Barrack 2d, scale 1m, looking NE	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00789	Barrack entrance 2e, vegetation enclosure at top right, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00790	Entrance 2e, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00791	Entrance 2e, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00792	Entrance 2e, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00793	Vegetation enclosure at NW corner of barrack/workshop 2e, looking NW	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00794	Barrack entrance 2c, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00795	Entrance 2c, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00796	Entrance 2c, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00797	Entrance 2c, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00798	Barrack entrance 2b, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00799	Entrance 2b, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00800	Entrance 2b, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140720 - Marble Island Walkover			Sheet <u>2</u> of <u>4</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	DSC00801	Barrack entrance 2a scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00802	ML surveying a drain between barrack 2a (left) and barrack 2b (right), the area behind him still looks wet, looking NW	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00803	Entrance 2a, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00804	Entrance 2a, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00806	Detail of entrance 2a, wooden boards held in position by wooden pegs, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00807	Workshop end of barrack 2a, door on the ground, but no clear indication of doorway in embankment, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00808	Comparison of 2a with side of workshop 2b, no clear doorway, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00809	Workshop 2c, no clear door, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00810	Workshop 2d, no clear door, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00811	Back of workshop 2d, a clear doorway in embankment, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00812	Back of workshop 2d, a clear doorway in embankment, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00813	Back of workshop 2e, doorway(?) not as clear, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00814	Side of workshop 2e, vegetation enclosure in NW corner, what happened to the founding beams?, scale 1m, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00815	Back of workshop 2b, no clear doorway, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00816	Back of workshop 2c, no clear doorway, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00817	Half an 'A' from a name board, scale in cm	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00818	House entrance 1c, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00819	Entrance 1c, imprints of beams, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00820	Did 1c have a shed?, looking E	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00821	1c shed foundation?, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00822	Refuse heap, looking W	FK, 20/07/14

PHOTOGRAPHIC INDEX			
140720 - Marble Island Walkover			Sheet <u>3</u> of <u>4</u>
B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	DSC00823	House entrance 1b, grasses, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00824	House entrance 1a, grasses not as obvious, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00825	Entrance 1a, grasses after grazing?, scale in cm	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00826	House 1a, shed entrance, more grasses?, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00827	House 1a, name board 'Camp Mansfield', original or not?	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00828	House 1a, use of corrugated iron, probably taken from workshops at Quarry 3, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00829	Location of radio antenna (3), looking SW	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00830	Central to antenna: a wooden plank, a wooden post, and a dug hole, scale 1m	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00831	Close-up of plank and post	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00832	Finds from across the settlement	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00833	Previously unrecorded feature, pump house?, but the water pipe lies to the E of it?! scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00834	Feature was approximately square, outline by cobbles, two areas of 'activity'?, scale 1m, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00835	Soil of one half more disturbed than the other, digging?, or removing of machinery?, scale 1m, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00836	Feature stood on the ridge between the settlement and the watery valley, scale 1m, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00837	Feature seemingly had a stove made by Smith and Wellstood, scale 10cm	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00838	Lower mandible of a fox, was feature a fox shed?, or a chicken pen?, or a pumping station?	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00839	Presence of wire support cage idea	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00840	Stone setting at stream edge, access point to water?, or foundation to a bridge?, looking W	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00841	Earthworks for the stationary crane at Quarry 3, looking N	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00842	Cobbles and boulders for ballast	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00843	Location of GPR Grid 5, looking NE	FK, 20/07/14

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140720 - Marble Island Walkover

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B/W or C/P or C/S or Digital	Film No / Shot No e.g. (1/2)	Location, Main Feature/s, Scale/s, Orientation, Remarks (e.g. weather, lighting conditions, bracketing)	Date & Initials
Digital	DSC00844	There would have been a second workshop here, were parts of it used to build the 'strange' ruin?, looking S	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00845	Hard streaks in the marble	FK, 20/07/14
Digital	DSC00846	Recent crack in the marble	FK, 20/07/14

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Appendix 3

Vegetation survey in the former settlement

A3.1 Map of vegetation survey

The map indicates the positions of the vegetation exclosures, which were erected in June and removed in August 2014.

It also shows the results of the visual survey of the unexclosed vegetation, in particular the presence of newly appearing plant species, mostly grasses, as black dots and small circles. Where the concentrations were found to be very high, the areas have been shaded.

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A17 (4 Aug 2014, 16:18h)

Exclosed

1:	29b	32	16	
2:	13	24	29	5
3:	4b	20	14	
4:	18b	25	13	
5:	23	30	29	3
6:	12	24	17	
7:	14	20	9	
8:	8bs	20	15	
9:	15b	23	24	4
10:	17b	29	12	

Notes:

Puccinelia & paardestaart

Unexclosed, Puccinelia

1:	3b	12b	1	
2:	3b	10b		
3:	12b	3b	6b	7
4:	2b	16b	3	
5:	3b	11b	15	
6:	8b	8		
7:	12b	4		
8:	11b	1b	4	
9:	7b	7b		
10:	4bs	10b	5b	16

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A11 (4 Aug 2014, 16:33h)

Exclosed

1:	9bd	15s	24	26	Notes: Equisetum
2:	13	21	25		
3:	21	36	21		
4:	19	37	39		
5:	12	26	17		
6:	15	21	30	12	
7:	20	23	33	2	Poa
8:	15	33	18		
9:	13b	27b	32		
10:	15	38	33		

Unexclosed

1:	4b	20			Notes:
2:	8b	15			
3:	4b	19	5		
4:	23b	15			
5:	15b	2			
6:	8bd	11	32		
7:	13b	20			
8:	6b	17b	18		
9:	4b	6b	19		
10:	23b	12b	29		

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A12 (4 Aug 2014, 16:48h)

Exclosed				Notes:
1:	21td	44	72	
2:	29td	34	68	
3:	26	35		
4:	19	36	27	
5:	22	39	8	
6:	22	20		
7:	34	72	30	
8:	25b	42	15	
9:	24b	51	9	
10:	22b	38	11	

Unexclosed				Notes:
1:	27b	29		
2:	31b	18		
3:	2b	28b	5	
4:	8b	36b		
5:	4b	29b		
6:	2b	33b	9	
7:	4b	30b	2	
8:	35b	17		
9:	36b	25		
10:	3b	24		

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A13 (4 Aug 2014, 17:00h)

Exclosed

1:	31	65	55
2:	58	72	
3:	28	45	21
4:	24	68	
5:	28	54	36
6:	36	37	
7:	23	39	4
8:	25b	44	7
9:	16b	47	41
10:	23	38	28

Notes:

Saxifraga svalbardensis, Poa

Unexclosed

1:	23b	1b	16
2:	15	38	
3:	8b	65	
4:	0b	40	
5:	15	30b	
6:	19	19b	39
7:	25b	1b	21
8:	19b	13	
9:	10b	26	
10:	22b	5	

Notes:

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A14 (4 Aug 2014, 17:17h)

Exclosed

1:	33	47	21
2:	19b	53	33
3:	27b	46	33
4:	30b	61	55
5:	20b	36	
6:	5b	30b	42
7:	6b	31	34
8:	27	41	
9:	22b	38	29
10:	35b	41	

Notes:

Poa

Unexclosed

1:	10b	21b	35b	25
2:	3b	11		
3:	11b	28	31	
4:	10b	13b	12	
5:	21b	8b	15	
6:	21b	13b	16	
7:	13b	13b	25	
8:	12b	31	13	
9:	29b	13		
10:	34	28		

Notes:

8 bloeiaren exclosed,
1 bloeibaar unexclosed

A3.2 Measurements of grass tillers (mm) in vegetation exclosures

Exclosure A15 (4 Aug 2014, 17:33h)

Exclosed

1:	25s	29	29	15
2:	21	17	7	
3:	6b	14	14	3
4:	18	18	17	
5:	13	18	14	
6:	17b	21	20	
7:	18	19		
8:	14bs	30	30	17
9:	12b	11		
10:	22	24	26	6

Notes:

Poa -->
polletje -->
zacht plat

Unexclosed

1:	21	28	24	4
2:	27	26	28	12
3:	18	19	23	2
4:	23	22	20	7
5:	28	35	16	
6:	19	18	16b	
7:	16s	19	22	
8:	18	22	15	
9:	22	25	13	
10:	20	22	17	

Notes:

polletje Poa

Appendix 4

Reconnaissance dive in Peirsonhamna

Zusammenfassung der Ergebnisse der Tauchuntersuchungen in Peirsonhamna (Bloomstrand / Kongsfjord / Svalbard) – 24.06.2014 - 10.07.2014

„Are there any traces of human activity under water?“

Einleitung	
Fragestellung	1
Tauchgebiet und Untersuchungszeitraum	1
Durchgeführte Tauchgänge	2
Ergebnisse	
Gebiet I „The crane“	3
Gebiet II „The stream“	7
Gebiet III „The fisheries station“	7
Gebiet IV (Mid-harbour)	9

Einleitung

Fragestellung:

Im März 2014 wurde angefragt, ob die Tauchgruppe des Alfred-Wegener-Instituts im Sommer 2014 einige Taucheinsätze im Bereich Peirsonhamna (Bloomstrandhalvøya / Kongsfjord / Svalbard) durchführen könne, um dort der Frage nachzugehen, ob sich unter Wasser noch anthropogene Spuren der ehemaligen Siedlung Ny London finden ließen. Im Bereich dieser Siedlung wurde zu Beginn des 20. Jahrhunderts Marmor abgebaut und zur Verschiffung nach England verladen.

Die Taucharbeiten sollten nach Möglichkeit im Juni / Juli 2014 im Rahmen der diesjährigen Spitzbergen-Sommer-Kampagne der AWI Tauchgruppe stattfinden.

Auftraggeber der Arbeiten war Dr. Frigga Kruse (Abt. Polar Historical Archaeology), Arctic Centre University of Groningen.

Tauchgebiet und Untersuchungszeitraum:

Die Bucht Peirsonhamna liegt am südlichen Ufer der Insel Bloomstrandhalvøya im Kongsfjord (West-Spitzbergen) auf ca. 78°57'41.06" N und 12° 2'38.83" E (Abb. 1). Die Bucht öffnet sich in südliche Richtung zum Kongsfjord, an ihrem nördlichen und westlichen Ufer finden sich einige verbliebene Gebäude sowie Maschinen- und Verladeanlagen der ehemaligen Siedlung Ny London. Die Bucht ist ca. 250 m bis 300 m breit (+/- Ost - West) und ca. 250 m bis 300 m tief (+/- Nord – Süd). Die maximale Wassertiefe im Inneren der Bucht beträgt (abhängig vom Gezeitenstand) ca. 6 - 7 m. Der Grund ist im Wesentlichen sandig bis feinsandig, an der westlichen und östlichen Küste felsig und im Bereich des nördlichen Strandes kiesig.

In Absprache mit Dr. Frigga Kruse wurden 4 mögliche Tauchgebiete innerhalb der Bucht ausgewählt, in denen eine möglichst große Wahrscheinlichkeit auf Funde gegeben war. Die Gebiete sind im Ergebnisteil im Einzelnen aufgeführt.

Abb. 1: Die Bucht Peirsonhamna am südlichen Ufer der Insel Bloomstrandhalvøya

Als Untersuchungszeitraum wurde Mitte Juni bis spätestens Mitte Juli vereinbart, tatsächlich fanden alle Tauchgänge im Zeitraum vom 24.06.2014 bis zum 10.07.2014 statt.

Durchgeführte Tauchgänge:

Insgesamt wurden im o.g. Untersuchungszeitraum 4 Taucheinsätze mit zusammen 8 Tauchgängen in Peirsonhamna durchgeführt. Alle Tauchgänge verliefen dabei in Übereinstimmung mit der GUV-Regel „Einsatz von Forschungstauchern“ (BGR / GUV-R 2112, Ausgabe 2011).

Es wurde vom vor Anker liegenden Boot unter Einsatz einer Signalleine getaucht, die Tauchzeiten betragen zwischen 27 und 53 Minuten, die maximale Tauchtiefe betrug dabei 6,2 m.

Fundstücke wurden vom Taucher mit kleinen Bojen und Grundgewichten markiert, anschließend - je nach Möglichkeit - fotografiert, vermessen und gegebenenfalls gezeichnet (s. Ergebnisteil).

An den Taucheinsätzen beteiligte Taucher waren:
Max Schwanitz – Taucheinsatzleiter (AWI-Bremerhaven)
Anke Bender (AWI Bremerhaven)
Sina Petrowski (AWI Sylt)

Ergebnisse

Gebiet I „The crane“:

Das Gebiet I liegt an der Westseite der Bucht unterhalb einer markanten Felsnase, auf der heute noch Reste einer kranartigen Verladeeinrichtung zu sehen sind. Der Bereich um diese Felsnase wurde in ca. 1 m bis ca. 3,5 m Tiefe mehrfach betaucht, hier wurden die meisten Fundstücke gefunden.

Die Funde sind im Folgenden aufgeführt und beschrieben, aufgrund des dichten Algenbewuchses an dieser Stelle ist aber nicht auszuschließen, dass noch weitere Artefakte dort liegen, die bei dieser ersten Untersuchung übersehen wurden. Den gefundenen Gegenständen wurden zunächst Arbeitsnamen zugeordnet, wobei diese nicht unbedingt der wahren Natur der Gegenstände entsprechen müssen.

Es wurden folgende Gegenstände gefunden:

a) „Rad“ (Abb. 2 - 3)

Es handelt sich hierbei um eine radartiges Metallscheibe mit folgenden Maßen: \varnothing ca. 11 – 11,5 cm, \varnothing des inneren Rings ca. 5,5 – 6 cm, Dicke ca. 3 cm.

Abb. 2: „Rad“ (Foto: © Max Schwanitz)

Abb. 3: „Rad“ (Foto: © Max Schwanitz)

b) „Schienen“ (Abb. 4 - 7)

Im Gebiet I wurden mehrere schienenartige Metallteile gefunden. Diese waren jeweils zwischen ca. 1,64 m und ca. 2,5 m lang und zu großen Teilen mit Sediment bedeckt.

Abb. 4

Abb. 5

Abb. 6

Abb. 7

Abb. 4 - 7: „Schienen“
(Fotos: © Max Schwanitz)

c) „Gewindestange“ (Abb. 8 - 10)

Hierbei handelt es sich um eine Stange von 1,13 m Länge, die an beiden Enden mit Sechskantmutter von 4 cm \varnothing versehen ist. Im Endbereich weist die Stange Gewinde auf, jedoch nicht über die ganze Länge.

Abb. 8

Abb. 9

Abb. 8 - 10: „Gewindestange“
(Fotos: © Max Schwanitz)

Abb. 10

d) „Werkzeug“ (Abb. 11 - 12)

Als „Werkzeug“ wurde eine ca. 3 m lange massive Metallstange bezeichnet. Diese scheint geschmiedet zu sein und hat, wie auf den Bildern zu sehen, einen sechseckigen Querschnitt.

Abb. 11 – 12: „Stehblech“ (Fotos: © Max Schwanitz)

e) „Stehblech“ (Abb. 13 - 14)

Dieses Fundstück konnte nicht komplett gesehen bzw. erkannt werden, da es teilweise von einem Felsbrocken bedeckt ist. Es handelt sich um eine auffällig geformte Platte aus Metall, die allerdings komplett mit Krustenrotalgen bewachsen ist. Die Platte hat eine Aufkantung am Rand, und eine gewellte (Unter-?)Kante und weist eine Seitenlänge (soweit sichtbar) von ca. 57 cm auf.

Abb. 13 – 14: „Stehblech“ (Fotos: © Max Schwanitz)

f) „Lochblech“ (Abb. 15 - 16)

Bei dem „Lochblech“ genannten Gegenstand handelt es sich um eine dünne Metallplatte, die flach auf dem Sandgrund liegt und zunächst nur durch die rostrote Verfä-

bung des Sediments zu erkennen ist. Die Platte hat eine Seitenlänge von ca. 40 cm auf 80 cm und weist nahe einer der Schmalseiten ein markantes rechteckiges Loch auf.

Abb. 15 – 16: „Lochblech“ (Fotos: © Max Schwanitz)

Gebiet II „The stream“:

Dieses Gebiet liegt am nördlichen Ufer der Bucht und umfasst die Mündung eines kleinen (Schmelzwasser-) Flusses. In diesem Gebiet wurde bei einem Tauchgang bis in ca. 3 m Tiefe nichts gefunden.

Gebiet III „The fisheries station“:

Diese Stelle liegt am westlichen Ufer der Bucht, hier wurden bei Tauchgängen die folgenden Gegenstände gefunden:

g) „Kran“ (Abb. 17 – 22)

Hiermit wurde eine Konstruktion aus drei Metallstangen bezeichnet, die am Rande des vorgelagerten Felsbuckels in einer Wassertiefe von ca. 2 m bis 2,5 m gefunden wurde. Die Stangen sind jeweils ca. 3,5 m bis 4,3 m lang und liegen in einer Art Dreieck übereinander. Die Stangen weisen an Ihren enden z.T. Schäkel, evtl. auch Kettenglieder auf. Das Ende einer Stange scheint gebrochen zu sein, evtl. ist die Stange hohl. Wie diese Stangen zusammenhängen bzw. ob sie evtl. nur lose übereinander liegen, lässt sich ohne Entfernung des Algenaufwuchses nicht sagen.

Abb. 17 – 22: „Kran“ (Fotos / Zeichnung: © Max Schwanitz)

h) „Klammer“ (Abb. 23)

Hierbei handelt es sich um eine in ca. 2,5 m Wassertiefe gefundene U-förmige Metallklammer von ca. 1,5 cm Stärke und ca. 32 cm Länge, die kurzen Seiten weisen jeweils ca. 6,5 bis 7 cm Länge auf.

Abb. 23: „Klammer“ (Zeichnung: © Anke Bender / Sina Petrowski)

i) „Metallteil“ (Abb. 24)

Hierbei handelt es sich um ein undefiniertes Metallstück von ca. 86 cm Länge und ca. 5 cm bis 8 cm Breite, welches im Gebiet III gefunden wurde.

Abb. 24: „Metallteil“ (Zeichnung: © Anke Bender / Sina Petrowski)

Gebiet IV „Mid-harbour“:

Hierbei ist ein Bereich in der Mitte der Bucht gemeint. In diesem Gebiet wurde bei einem Tauchgang bis in > 6 m Tiefe nichts gefunden. Auch bei früheren Tauchgängen für wissenschaftliche arbeiten wurden in diesem Gebiet keine auffälligen anthropogenen Spuren gefunden.

Für eventuelle Rückfragen stehe ich gern zur Verfügung:

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Appendix 5

Newly recorded archaeology

A5.1 Map of newly recorded archaeological features, July 2014

Where possible, the original names as applied in NEC documents or as evident in historical photographs have been used. The letters mark locations that can be found back in the list of newly recorded archaeological features in Appendix A5.2.

A5.2 Newly recorded archaeological features		
Site: Blomstrand, Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen		
Sheet <u> </u> 1 <u> </u> of <u> </u> 3 <u> </u>		
	Photos	Initial, Date
Observations, preliminary interpretation, location on map A5.1		
Ballast stones , for use on the crane that once stood here (see below), also parts of a large derrick, location A in map A6.1: south of No. 3 Quarry	P1030912	FK, 12/07/14
Crane foundation , a crane similar to that at the shore stood here and was removed to Camp Millar, A: south of No. 3 Quarry	P1030915	FK, 12/07/14
Borehole B5-68 , the 5th of a series drilled in 1968; a calendar from 1968 survives in one of the huts on site (see Appendix A5.3) which states when the drillers arrived on site and which holes were drilled when (B5: 8 Aug), clearly meant to investigate the marble but no record or report has been found yet, any connection with Siggerud (1960)?, B: NE corner of No. 3 Quarry	P1030925	FK, 12/07/14
Tool marks of exploration, these occur in many places on the outcrop, but location C is a particularly good example: individual blows with a crowbar can be counted here which served to exposed the streaks in the marble, scale 1m, C: W of No. 3 Quarry	P1030932, P1030934, P1030935, P1030936	FK, 12/07/14
Drill holes , these occur in many places on the outcrop, they may have been intended for shots of dynamite, rock samples or to secure large drilling rigs may also be options	P1030955, P1030956	FK, 12/07/14
Borehole B1-68 , drilled July 27, 1968, no record or report known, D: W of Winter Quarry	P1030972	FK, 12/07/14
Borehole B2-68 , drilled July 30, 1968, no record or report known, E: S of Winter Quarry	P1030981, P1030982	FK, 12/07/14
Possible slipway , a natural slip surface and maybe a fault but it lies in line with the railway embankment ca. 100m to the N, has this been altered by the company to become a slipway?, F: S of railway embankment and No. 2 Quarry	P1040021, P1040024	FK, 12/07/14
No. 2 Quarry , although recognised as a quarry by LASHIPA in 2008, it has since become evident that this must be what the NEC called No. 2 Quarry, G: quarry recorded at 7a in 2008	P1040034	FK, 12/07/14
Plug and feather , tool marks and actual tools at No. 2 Quarry prove that the stone was split manually using the plug-and-feather technique, scale 1m, G: No. 2 Quarry	P1040041, P1040044, P1040050	FK, 12/07/14
Early borehole , a borehole had been sunk into the outcrop seemingly before No. 2 Quarry was opened, scenario 1: the quarry was opened in 1911, so the borehole is from earlier that year (unlikely), scenario 2: part of the quarry was opened in 1911, but the borehole was drilled to one side in 1912/13 and work in the quarry continued afterwards, when compared to Booth's Day Book (Appendix A1.3), borehole 3 is a good candidate but it was cemented, borehole 5 is an option, G: in No. 2 Quarry	P1040052, P1040053, P1040055	FK, 12/07/14
Construction pits , next to the railway embankment there are obvious pits (down to the bedrock) from which material for the embankment was taken, H: next to embankment recorded as 12b in 2008	P1040056, P1040406, P1040407, P1040408	FK, 12/07/14
Borehole 1912/13 , this was one of the cemented holes drilled by Booth that winter, does it lie on a crack?, it was blocked at a shallow depth, J: W of No. 2 Quarry	P1040057, P1040071	FK, 12/07/14
Survey points 1928 , are these to markers related to Nobile's <i>Italia</i> expedition in 1928? K: beneath the crane at the shore and on a concrete pillar to the E of Peirsonhamna	P1040080, P1040346	FK, 12/07/14

A5.2 Newly recorded archaeological features

Site: Blomstrand, Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen

Sheet 2 of 3

	Photos	Initial, Date
Observations, preliminary interpretation, location on map A6.1		
Smithy , was it in use pre- or post-WWI? Scenario 1: the galvanised corrugated iron (GCI) on use elsewhere on site and the stove from the Columbian Stoveworks on use elsewhere on Spitsbergen suggest pre-war, scenario 2: it does not lie on the railway line and is remotely closer to the Winter Quarry: post-war?, scenario 3: it's not a smithy at all but a pumping station associated with the water pipe coming from the N, the bricks are not marked, L: NW of the Winter Quarry	P1040101, P1040102, P1040103	FK, 12/07/14
Diamond corer , parts of the corers used in 1912/13 can still be found on site: they can be seen in a photo of Booth's team in 1913, M: workshop E of Winter Quarry, 1913 storehouse, stream bed	P1040112	FK, 12/07/14
Water pipe , the water pipe near the Winter Quarry can be followed to its source, there appears to have been a wooden dam but no pumping station, this supports the notion that the 'smithy' may have been a pumping station, N: N of Winter Quarry	P1040174, P1040175, P1040178	FK, 12/07/14
Path of least resistance , although one could walk (almost) anywhere at all, paths begin to form, outside of map area	P1040191, P1040196	FK, 12/07/14
Live fox trap or self-shooting trap? Outside of map area	P1040192, P1040193	FK, 12/07/14
Water pipe , lying in a small gully that appears to have dried up a long time ago, outside map area	P1040215	FK, 12/07/14
Barrel , had puzzled LASHIPA in 2008 but historical photographs have shown that it was used for water storage on the channelers, O: S of 1913 storehouse	P1040239	FK, 12/07/14
Explosion pits , these are conical pits with circular spoil, most likely the results of shot being placed in the ground, perhaps to search for bedrock under the overburden, plants may seek refuge in the hollow (shelter from wind, more moisture?) but have not grown back on the spoil, P: on the plain between embankments and near Italian trig point	P1040246, P1040249, P1040349, P1040350	FK, 12/07/14
Fox traps , two in same location, one with stone, one without: replacing one another?, Q: vantage point near dynamite shed (R) overlooking settlement, q: a third fox trap next to Italian trig point	P1040250, P1040253, P1040264, P1040343	FK, 12/07/14
Dynamite , several small sticks were found around the fox traps (can also be orange), Q: vantage point near dynamite shed (R)	P1040254, P1040259, P1040265, P1040269, P1040428	FK, 12/07/14
Dynamite shed , a small shed made of imported roughly dressed granite blocks, some GCI, large sticks of dynamite with a London trademark, door posts show signs of burning, R: in a rock alcove well away from other structures	P1040272, P1040286, P1040290	FK, 12/07/14
Antenna , mapped by LASHIPA as a borehole in 2008 but more likely to be two or three masts of an antenna, Nobile?, S: NW of Italian trig point	P1040352, P1040353, P1040355	FK, 12/07/14
Impact of tourism , this trail in the snow shows the amount of soil carried onto it by walkers, wind-blown has been discounted, is this significant?	P1040356, P1040357	FK, 12/07/14
No. 1 Quarry , while this has been recognised as an early quarry in 2008, documents have since shown this to be the NEC's No. 1 Quarry opened in 1911, it was abandoned due to poor quality and being close to sea, T: at the shore W of the crane	P1040416, P1040417	FK, 12/07/14

A5.2 Newly recorded archaeological features

Site: Blomstrand, Kongsfjorden, Spitsbergen

Sheet 3 of 3

	Photos	Initial, Date
Observations, preliminary interpretation, location on map A5.1		
Submerged items , occasionally light condition were such that one could see into the water, no submerged constructions or items were seen	P1040440	FK, 12/07/14
Early borehole , to the E of No. 3 Quarry was a borehole that was not labelled as one of the 1968 ones, it may have been sunk in 1912/13, it was not cemented, U: E of No. 3 Quarry	P1040460, P1040461	FK, 12/07/14
Non-archaeology , there are features on the site that should not be called archaeology although they may comprise archaeological items, stove by Smith and Wellstood Ltd of Bonnybridge (Scotland)	P1040471, P1040472	FK, 12/07/14
Curiosities , large carbon rods once used in batteries	P1040479, P1040480	FK, 12/07/14
Fisheries station , what has been the impact of this 1930s activity on the local ecosystem?	P1040511	FK, 12/07/14
Quarry A13 , name given by H. Leech in 1920, I often refer to the Lighthouse Quarry for clarity among colleagues, including two boreholes	P1040616 - P1040677, P1040714 - P1040758	FK, 12/07/14
Camp name boards , the remains of the camps' name boards can be found among the houses, special artefacts!, the current 'Camp Mansfield' was not called that originally, the sign is not original either but made of original components	DSC00781, DSC00817, DSC00827, DSC00832	FK, 12/07/14
Barrack construction , the barracks had a separate workshop or store, which probably had doors in the N wall	DSC00812, DSC00813	FK, 12/07/14
Structure of unknown purpose , previously unmapped, interior division into a 'green' part and a 'rough' part, water pipes, some bricks, some natural stone, stove parts: Smith and Wellstood, fox mandible, thin wire, unlikely pumping station, fox cage? chickens?, W: N of 1913 storehouse	DSC00833 - DSC00839	FK, 12/07/14
Retaining wall at stream , including possible wall/building, was this a place to reach the water (drinking, washing) or to cross the water?, X: E of 1913 storehouse	DSC00840	FK, 12/07/14
Workshops , LASHIPA could not interpret a ruin and a concrete foundation in 2008, it has since been shown that the two workshops NW of the crane were some of the earliest buildings on site, the concrete foundation had either been found to be excessive or there werer problems with it drying, in any case: a workshop was removed from here to the S of No. 3 Quarry, Y: original workshop NW of crane, relocated workshop S of No. 3 Quarry	LASHIPA Project, or historical photos in Appendix A6	FK, 12/07/14

A5.3 Calendar of 1968

This calendar has survived in one of the huts on Blomstrand. It shows when a team of drillers arrived on the island in 1968, when a series of boreholes were completed and when the drillers left again. A record or report of their work is not known. If it could be found it would provide infinitely more information about the quality of the marble. (Photo: F. Kruse.)

Appendix 6

Results of archival research

A6.6 Repeat photography

Since repeat photography was not the primary objective behind the recent photographs, most are only approximations. Many of the photographs have been cropped.

The map indicates the positions from which historical photographs were taken. The numbers correspond to those in the following list.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(1) Mining settlement as seen upon arrival in Peirsonhamna post-1913, looking N. Unknown source.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(2) Cows having been brought to Marble Island in spring 1913. The photograph was taken at the back of the settlement, looking SE. Barr et al. 2012, 103.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(2) The photograph was taken at the back of the settlement, looking SE. It shows the backs of two of the original barracks or "Camps" which were removed to Ny Ålesund in the 1950s. Barr et al. 2012, 103.

The photograph shows one of the four relocated 'London houses', London 1. The differences between the original and these buildings are obvious. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(3) The mining settlement in 1938, looking NE. Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI).

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(4) A completed barrack, Camp Warburg, in 1916. NPI.

London 1, Ny Ålesund. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(5) The radio antenna (1919) was still standing after the 'London houses' had been removed in the 1950s, looking NE. NPI.

F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(6) Stationary crane from Aberdeen operating at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking N. Polarmuseet Tromsø.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(7) Railway and granite-built dynamite storage shed beyond in 1912, looking SW. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(8) Railway and dynamite shed in 1912. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(9) Initial workshops or storehouses in 1912, looking W. Polarmuseet.

Definitely not the best reconstruction ever but recognisable. Note the concrete floor centre left. D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(9) Initial workshop or storehouses in 1912, looking W. Polarmuseet.

Relocated workshop S of No. 3 Quarry, looking N. B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(10) Mining settlement in 1912 (prior to storehouse construction in 1913), looking NW. Polarmuseet.

F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(11) Channelers and crane at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking SE. Polarmuseet.

F. Kruse 2014

A6.6 Repeat photography

(11) Channelers and crane at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking SE. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(~12) Crane from Aberdeen at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking W. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(13) Crane at natural quay in 1912, looking SE. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(14) Storehouse completed in 1913, looking E. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

An unidentified quarry in summer. British Geological Survey (BGS).

(15) A mirror image of the Winter Quarry (D. Avango 2008) was considered as was a location at the natural rock quay but without success.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(16) A finished barrack, probably Camp Peirson in 1911, looking N. BGS.

London 1, Ny Ålesund. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(17) A barrack under construction, probably Camp Peirson in 1911, looking NW. BGS.

London 2, Ny Ålesund. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(18) Storehouse completed in 1913, looking N. BGS.

F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(19) Camps Maples and Lagercrantz in 1912/13, looking N. D. Booth 1912/13.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(20) Camp Peirson in 1913, looking N. D. Booth 1912/13.

London 1, Ny Ålesund. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(22) Channler at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking S. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(23) Channler at No. 3 Quarry in 1912, looking SE. Polarmuseet.

D. Avango 2008.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(24) Claim post at the present day trig point at 37m AOD, 1912 or 1913, looking S. Polarmuseet.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(24) Claim post at the present day trig point at 37m AOD, 1912 or 1913, looking S. Polarmuseet.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(25) Mining settlement after the storehouse construction in 1913, looking S. Polarmuseet.

B. Koster 2014.

A6.6 Repeat photography

(4) First barrack under construction, Camp Peirson in 1911, looking S. Polarmuseet.

London 1, Ny Ålesund. F. Kruse 2014.

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

Documentary evidence	<i>Preliminary interpretations and lines of enquiry</i>
<p>1902</p> <p>Home Office, Mines and quarries: general report and statistics, 1902-1912</p> <p>See Appendix A6.2</p>	<p><i>The figures seem to suggest two things: either the global production of marble was picking up or the recording of the global production of marble was picking up – there is a difference that undermines the reliability of these figures.</i></p> <p><i>The HO statistics were readily available from, for instance, mining institutes. Anyone with some marble to spare might have thought it a good time to invest in the dimension stone. Unfortunately, the record ends in 1911. Renwick being published in 1909 already (see below) will not have a better time series.</i></p>
<p>1905</p> <p>Home Office (1906) Mines and quarries: general report and statistics for 1905, London: HM Stationary Office</p> <p>Greece. Marble. – The marble industry of Greece is of considerable importance, and many of the quarries known to the ancients are being re-worked by English companies, viz., at Larissa and Pentelicon on the mainland, and in the islands of Skyros, Eubœa, and Tinos. One British Company (Mamor Limited), obtained 5,105 cubic metres of marble from its quarries in 1903, 3,258 cubic metres in 1904, and 2,1198 cubic metres in 1905.</p>	<p><i>Interesting that the HO should pinpoint Greece and later Italy and Norway when France and Belgium are the closest and biggest producers at the time. Of course an English Co. operating here, but it also indicates other market forces at work. A company file has not been found.</i></p>
<p>1906</p> <p>The Iona Marble Co., 1906 – 1937, practically inactive in 1909</p> <p>Company file included in Appendix A6.3</p>	<p><i>One of the British companies I could find the company file of in order to see if British firms were successful. This one was not.</i></p>
<p>1907</p> <p>Skye Marble Ltd., 1907 – 1915</p> <p>Company file included in Appendix A6.4</p>	<p><i>One of the British companies I could find the company file of in order to see if British firms were successful. This one was not.</i></p>
<p>1907</p> <p>Home Office (1909) Mines and quarries: general report and statistics for 1907, Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics, London: HM Stationary Office.</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – The well-known Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of Triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary marble, the quarries furnish many</p>	<p><i>No mention of a British firm, but US and UK form a third of the Italian market.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>coloured varieties, each of them known in commerce by its special name.</p> <p>The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1907 to 17,903 persons. 274,482 tons of marble were exported during that year, about one-third of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p>	
<p>1908</p> <p>Home Office (1910) Mines and quarries: general report and statistics for 1908. Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Greece. Marble. – The marble industry of Greece is of considerable importance, and many of the quarries known to the ancients are being re-worked by English companies, viz., at Larissa and Pentelicon on the mainland, and in the islands of Skyros, Eubœa, and Tinos. A British Company (Mamor Limited), owns several marble quarries throughout Greece, as well as those of Tinos and Paros. The output of this Company in 1908 was 3,916 cubic metres or 11,448 metric tons valued at £24,532. The Parian marble has been celebrated from the time of the ancients.</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – The well-known Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of Triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary marble, the quarries furnish many coloured varieties, each of them known in commerce by its special name.</p> <p>The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1908 to 17,395 persons. 246,605 tons of marble were exported during that year, about one-third of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p> <p>Norway. Marble. – Fauske, in Nordland, is the chief marble centre.</p>	<p><i>See above for Greece and Italy.</i></p> <p><i>First mention of a marble quarry at Fauske in Norway, which was seemingly not known to Renwick (1909).</i></p>
<p>(Following the entry above)</p> <p>Norwegian Rose AS (no date) Den Ankerske Marmorforetning. Available at: http://www.norwegianrose.no/norsk/den_ankerske_marmorforetning.htm (accessed 20 February 2015)</p> <p>Christian August Anker (born 1840 in Frederikshald, now Halden (Østfold), died 1912) was a Norwegian engineer and one of Norway's industrial pioneers. In the early 1880s, he began to show interest in the stone industry and bought marble deposits in Fauske (Nordland) as well as Ofoten (Nordland), Porsgrunn (Telemark), and Hadeland (Oppland). He founded the</p>	<p><i>Fauske is important because it lies just inside the Arctic Circle and it belonged to one Christian August Anker.</i></p> <p><i>Both, Anker and the NEC claimed the coal deposits on the south side of Kings Bay, Kongsfjorden. Although history has shown that the Norwegians had the more legitimate claim, the NEC later received compensation for coal mind during WWI. Long story, lots of fuzz.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>Anker Marble Company (<i>Den Ankerske Marmorforetning</i>) with the aim to quarry and to process Norwegian marble. In 1886, he also built a marble processing plant in Isebakke near Halden. The plant was located near the sea and had a sturdy pier at which boats delivered marble blocks from Fauske. At its peak, the plant employed 100 workers while the maximum employed at Fauske was 150. The company's products were exported to Sweden, England, and the Netherlands. Some was used in luxury building in Christiania (now Oslo). As the company grew from humble beginnings to a larger industrial complex, it refined its products and had many quarries and rights in Nordland, Trøndelag, as well as western and eastern Norway. It invested greatly into new equipment that by 1896, it was said to be so advanced that folks came from Italy and other countries to learn the operating techniques used. When exports decreased and the sales to Christiania fell, the company had to be rationalized. The primary stages of the work should be done in Fauske, while refining would take place in Denmark. In 1905, the plant in Isebakke was mostly torn down and shipped to Fauske, where it was rebuilt. Of the machines, some were sent to Fauske, others to Denmark. In the 1920s, marble wash basins were a major export commodity. It is said that in one week, 150 wash basins were sent to England only. The remainder of the company's history is inconsequential here. After changing hands, it still operates today under the name Norwegian Rose, owned by NORBLOCK AS.</p>	<p><i>Point being, Anker never seriously claimed the north side of Kongsfjorden, i.e. Marble Island. There is a half-hearted pencil sketch claim map that includes the whole of Kongsfjord but that can be disregarded here. And why would he? There is no coal there and he already possessed a marble quarry in a much better location.</i></p> <p><i>I tend to think the early rumours of the marble being bad quality were started by him or his. It is safe to speak of rumours at this point because no one had done any thorough investigation yet. Fauske, despite being better placed, had little to gain from competition from Spitsbergen. A rumour could easily be started, especially if the competition did not speak Norwegian, and work against the English. This evidence is circumstantial; no documents have been found to prove it.</i></p>
<p>1909</p> <p>Renwick, W. G. 1909. <i>Marble and marble working</i>. London: Crosby Lockwood and Son.</p>	<p><i>The author did not have time to read this in full prior to writing this report. Probably most of what there was to know about marble at the time.</i></p> <p><i>Renwick did not include anything about the marble quarries in Fauske, just inside the Arctic Circle in Norway (see below). Did he not know?</i></p> <p><i>Renwick was the NEC's marble expert on Marble Island for two summer seasons. What was his situation? Would he risk undermining his professionalism by not being objective?</i></p>
<p>1909</p> <p>Home Office (1911) <i>Mines and quarries: general report and statistics for 1909. Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics</i>, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary</p>	

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>marble, the quarries furnish many coloured varieties. The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1909 to 17,380 persons. 254508 tons of marble were exported during that year, about one-third of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p> <p>Norway. Marble. – Fauske, in Nordland, is the chief marble centre.</p>	
<p>1910</p> <p>Home Office (1912) Mines and quarries: general report with statistics for 1910. Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Greece. Marble. – Several quarries in Greece are being worked by English companies. The British Marmor, Limited, has now been reconstituted and bought by a new company “The Grecian Marbles (Marmor), Limited.”</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary marble, the quarries furnish many coloured varieties. The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1910 to 17,883 persons. 286160 tons of marble were exported during that year, about 30 per cent. of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p> <p>Norway. Marble. – Fauske, in Nordland, is the chief marble centre.</p>	<p><i>Only in 1908, the British Co. was apparently producing good marble. Reconstitutions often suggest that there has been trouble and that the figures were not correct.</i></p>
<p>1911</p> <p>Home Office (1914) Mines and quarries: general report with statistics for 1911. Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Greece. Marble. – Quarries for marble were worked in 1911 in the districts of Dionysos, Mani, Panormos, Paros, Skyros and Styres.</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary marble, the quarries furnish many coloured varieties.</p> <p>The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1911 to 18,964 persons. 300,986 tons of marble were exported during that year, about 27 per cent. of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p>	<p><i>No mention of a British company.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>Norway. Marble. – Fauske, in Nordland, is the chief marble centre. 400 tons of marble were exported in 1911.</p>	
<p>1912</p> <p>Home Office (1914) Mines and quarries: general report with statistics for 1912. Part IV. – Colonial and foreign statistics, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Greece. Marble. – Quarries for marble were worked in 1912 in the districts of Dionysos, Larissa, Panormos, Paros, Skyros and Styres.</p> <p>Italy. Marble. – Carrara marble is obtained from beds of crystalline limestone of triassic age, which in places attain the enormous thickness of more than 3,000 feet (1,000 m.). In addition to the finest statuary marble, the quarries furnish many coloured varieties. The quarries and dressing establishments of the Apuan Alps gave work during 1912 to 17,207 persons. 326,951 tons of marble were exported during that year, about 27 per cent. of which was sent to the United States and to Britain.</p> <p>Norway. Marble. – Fauske, in Nordland, is the chief marble centre.</p>	<p><i>The marble statistics end here. Marble wasn't all that important during the First World War...</i></p>
<p>1912/13</p> <p>David Booth (1912/13) Day Book</p> <p>See Appendix A1.3 Summary of historical borehole data, 1912/13</p>	<p><i>An invaluable and reliable contemporary account; it is remarkable that the NEC did not take it off Booth (seeing that it did not put the season's results into the best light) and it has survived with his family (copy in the author's possession)</i></p> <p><i>Booth clearly records that practically no solid cores were recovered in winter 1912/13 → compare to Leech (1920)</i></p> <p><i>Booth records the environmental impact of 11 apparently poorly provisioned men during that winter as well as the diseases that seemingly came with the first ship in spring 1913 → see Appendix 6.6</i></p> <p><i>[a pig was slaughtered, 127+ 'seagulls' and 6 seals were killed, cows were brought to site, no mention of reindeer or polar bears, dynamite was used, within six days of the ship arriving the first men fell ill]</i></p>
<p>1913</p> <p>Imperial Mineral Resources Bureau (1921) The mineral industry of the British Empire and foreign countries. Statistical summary (production, imports and exports) 1913-1920, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Marble no longer listed separately.</p>	<p><i>By the time of writing, a readily accessible source of British or global marble statistics had not been found.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>1914-18</p> <p>First World War</p>	<p><i>At the outbreak of war, the British voluntarily left Spitsbergen and took up military service.</i></p>
<p>1916</p> <p>Clapson, Mark (2009) <i>The Routledge companion to Britain in the twentieth century</i>, Abingdon: Routledge.</p> <p>1916: Ministry of Reconstruction established; it was responsible for demobilization, health, housing, national insurance and education.</p> <p>1918: Tudor Walters Report (October): the report of the committee chaired by Sir John Tudor Walters on housing and reconstruction was enormously influential on subsequent council housing. The report argued that 500,000 new dwellings were required [...]</p> <p>1919: Housing and Town Planning Act (Addison Act) (July): initiated the large-scale construction of council estates by local authorities through the provision of a central government subsidy to local councils. Hence government now took on the responsibility of providing housing for the working classes. A significant break with laissez-faire.</p> <p>1919: Housing (Additional Powers) Bill (December): expedited the process whereby councils were directly subsidized to build homes.</p>	<p><i>Although the link is seldom explicitly made, the Ministry of Reconstruction and decision about the construction of affordable housing may have had a crucial effect on the marble market.</i></p>
<p>1917</p> <p>Hansard, HC Deb 08 March 1917 vol 91 cc594-674, Civil Services and Revenue Department estimates 1917-18, Mr Watt (633):</p> <p>The point I desire to bring to his notice was the importation of marble for building purposes. The Department at 20, Carlisle Place, has given marked preference to several ports in Scotland, and has unfortunately shown a marked declination to give licenses for the import of marble to the great city of Glasgow.</p>	<p><i>Still there is marble import going on during the war.</i></p>
<p>1918</p> <p><i>Mining Journal</i> (1918) 'Building after the war', p. 350</p> <p>'The Committee of the Ministry of Reconstruction, who are studying the supply of building materials during a reconstruction period of two years after the war, has extended the date for returning enquiry forms to July 1 next. Unless the Committee is made fully aware of the prospective needs of consumers they profess themselves unable to estimate how far available supplies will meet the demands.'</p>	<p><i>Will marble have been one of these building materials? Most likely not. The market would have been limited.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>1919</p> <p>USGS (no date) Events affecting the U.S. nonfuel minerals industry 1900-2000. Available at: http://minerals.usgs.gov/ (accessed 20 February 2015).</p> <p>A timeline indicating economic recessions in 1919, 1920-21, 1923-24, 1927, 1929-1933; Gold Reserve Act 1934 fixing the gold price</p>	<p><i>A reminder that the post- and inter-war years were riddled with economic depressions both in the US and the UK. Not the best time for potential shareholders and subsidiary mining companies to be enthusiastic about Arctic investments.</i></p>
<p>1919</p> <p>Hansard, HC Deb 15 May 1919 vol 115 cc1829-922, Affairs in Egypt, Sir Martin Conway:</p> <p>great deposits of iron, quantities of wonderful marbles, and it is capable of producing an almost unlimited supply of those products of the fauna of the Arctic regions which in former days it produced</p>	<p><i>The Spitsbergen expert Conway makes a case for Arctic marble – but in a debate on Egypt! He is not being heard.</i></p>
<p>1919</p> <p>The original hand-written manuscript, notebook, and diary of Herbert Leech, marble manager in summer 1919, survive in Toronto, Canada. They are awaiting auction for the phenomenal sum approaching \$9900.</p> <p>(For more information, see http://www.mbenjaminkatzfinebooksraremanuscripts.com/?page=shop/flypage&product_id=1373).</p>	<p><i>Kruse failed to obtain the cooperation of the current owner and gain access to the papers in order to tap into and maximise their academic potential. There is a real danger of their becoming 'lost' in a private collection.</i></p> <p><i>The online summary hints at the documents speaking of much trouble with ships, provisions, and workers during the summer season.</i></p>
<p>1920</p> <p>Imperial Mineral Resources Bureau (1924) The mineral industry of the British Empire and foreign countries. Statistical summary (production, imports and exports) 1920-1922, London: HMSO.</p> <p>Marble no longer listed separately.</p>	<p><i>By the time of writing, a readily accessible source of British or global marble statistics had not been found.</i></p>
<p>1920</p> <p>Hansard, HC Deb 09 November 1920 vol 134 cc1029-148, Ministry of Health (Miscellaneous Provisions) Bill, Lieut.-Colonel Fremantle:</p> <p>As regards Clause 3 and the question of building control, I think most of the big authorities in London, and certainly the London County Council, have been doing their utmost to facilitate the proper supply of operatives for building houses, under housing schemes or under private enterprise, by diminishing luxury building, and one of the chief difficulties has</p>	<p><i>Some direct evidence that the restrictions on luxury building are having negative effects on the marble industry, in this case specialized workers.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>been [...] restricting buildings to what seem absolutely necessary for the needs of business as opposed to pleasure [...] we are at the present moment cutting off our noses to spite our face. We are stopping building in London, and at the same time building operatives can get high wages for building cinemas in some of the areas outside London. That is proposed to be met by this Clause 3, and I think it is an extremely necessary measure. I would say one point as regards the tribunal for stopping luxury building, and that is that I hope there will be a better representation of the operatives themselves on this tribunal, because a great deal depends upon the operatives' point of view. Luxury building is not simply a question of stopping down so much building in order to throw it into house building, but there is a great deal of employment in so-called luxury building for certain operatives that are not used at all in building houses. This class of men are thrown out of work entirely if you stop what is called luxury building. Work like marble cutting, and certain kinds of furnishing and decoration, must go on [...]</p>	
<p>1920</p> <p>Leech, H. W. (Dec 1920) <i>Report on various marble properties in Spitsbergen</i>, London: Northern Exploration Co. The full report is available in the Northern Exploration Co. file of the Norwegian Polar Institute Archive in Tromsø.</p> <p>See Appendix A1.4</p> <p>'many of the cores obtained were polished and sent to the London Office, and appear to be sound, attractive and good class marbles. I presume there is a report in the London Office by Mr. Miller, the Manager of this party, and this probably contains valuable information as to the quality and variety of marble at various depths. There is a report by Mr. Booth, the Mechanic, but this gives no detailed information of the marble at various depths.'</p>	<p><i>In light of the borehole logs of 1912/13 (see above), it is curious that Leech should report this.</i></p> <p><i>I consider this the first real evidence of fraud being committed by the NEC!!!</i></p> <p><i>Two scenarios: the cores in the London Office were either obtained elsewhere on site – or they were not obtained on Marble Island at all. The latter is likely, although Leech appears to have some success in relocating the different kinds. (Note: Leech is unaware of any foul play.)</i></p> <p><i>There are instances throughout Mansfield's involvement and NEC history of detrimental reports being strategically withheld – although it cannot be proven exactly by whom and at what times. This, however, is a clear indication of 'data' (in form of the cores) being manipulated.</i></p> <p><i>One of the things that struck me during fieldwork was how tidy the borehole locations were: could someone have swept them to hide any obviously broken cores?! (Not very likely but worth a thought...)</i></p>
<p>1920s</p> <p>Parliamentary debates about luxury building</p>	<p><i>An assumption that for as long as the debates on luxury building continue, the marble market is crippled.</i></p>
<p>1923</p> <p>Hansard, HC Deb 01 August 1923 vol 167 cc1543-658, Unemployment, Mr H. M. Butler:</p>	<p><i>A suggestion that the marble market is further under threat by the increasing use of imitations or alternatives.</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>[...] and only last week I have taken practical steps to help a capitalist to establish a new industry for the production of imitation marble.</p>																			
<p>1923, maybe later</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="188 383 778 1406"> <tr> <td data-bbox="188 383 352 636">	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Reddish brown traversed by broad white veins.”</p>	<p><i>In the early 1920s, one John Watson published a ‘List of the World’s Marbles’, which was printed in Through the Ages, the magazine of the US National Association of Marble Dealers between 1923 and 1932.</i></p> <p><i>It is not known how or if Watson was involved with the NEC.</i></p> <p><i>The early 1920s were not the best time for the Spitsbergen marbles to make a debut on the international stage. Nothing similar to this list has been discovered.</i></p>																
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Black with numerous white patches, traversed by a few slender brown markings. Another variety is dark gray and red clouded with angular patches of white.”</p>																	
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Gray and fawn colored with clouded white veins and slender brownish-red markings.”</p>																	
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Bluish fawn colored with white veins and slender pink markings.”</p>																	
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Gray with white veins and occasional slender brown markings.”</p>																	
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p><i>(See the individual entries for the description of these stones.)</i></p>																	
	<p>“Quarried on Marble Island off the coast of West Spitsbergen (or New Friesland), Norway.”</p>	<p>“Reddish brown traversed by broad white veins.”</p>																	
<p>1925</p> <p>HC Deb 04 March 1925 vol 181 c455W, Scotland, Alien’s Order 1920</p> <p>summary of permits granted and refused during the period 29 December 1923 and 31 December 1924: mosaic, terrazzo and marble workers, 43 granted, 20 refused</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but nothing significant.</i></p> <p><i>Included more to show the nature and depth of the documents thus far consulted.</i></p>																		
<p>1925</p> <p>HC Deb 09 December 1925 vol 189 cc493-4W, Royal Air Force (Cadets, Cranwell), Aliens Order 1920</p> <p>summary of permits granted and refused during the period 1 January 1925 and 30 September 1925, mosaic, terrazzo, and marble workers, 5 granted, 6</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but nothing significant.</i></p> <p><i>Included more to show the nature and depth of the documents thus far consulted.</i></p>																		

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

refused	
<p>1926</p> <p>HC Deb 08 February 1926 vol 191 cc660-2W, Italy</p> <p>imports from Italy in 1925, stones and slates (chiefly marble) declared value thereof 456 T.£, total imports £21,692,000</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but how must this information be judged?</i></p>
<p>1927</p> <p>HC Deb 03 March 1927 vol 203 cc581-3W, Aliens</p> <p>permits granted and refused for the year 1927, mosaic, terrazzo and marble workers, 2 granted, 11 refused</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but nothing significant.</i></p> <p><i>Included more to show the nature and depth of the documents thus far consulted.</i></p>
<p>1927</p> <p>HC Deb 07 April 1927 vol 204 cc2293-4W, Italian merchandise (imports)</p> <p>imported into GB and NI during 1926, marble (other than works of art) declared value £467,000, total imports £15,740,000</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but how must this information be judged?</i></p>
<p>1927</p> <p>Report of the Svalbard Commissioner, 1927</p> <p>Area No. 2. Blomstrandhalvøya. The area is limited by the following boundary lines: From point No. 32 on the south side of Blomstrandhamna [...], a straight line to point No. 33 north of Dyrevika [...]. Thence the shore line back to the starting point No. 32. (Points Nos. 32 and 33 are also boundary points of the area of Kings Bay Kul Comp. A/S). Area: 6.56 sp. Miles or 4,200 acres or 17.0 sq. kilometres.</p>	<p><i>All claims and claim disputes on Spitsbergen were finally settled by the Danish Commissioner in 1927, but the arbitration was costly for companies who had to pay a fee for every acre kept. So the NEC had to think long and hard whether its grossly inflated claims were actually worth anything.</i></p> <p><i>The fact that they kept Marble Island proved to me that they still thought something could be made of the resource. The current directors at least did not believe it was a fraud.</i></p> <p><i>Did anyone involved at this stage still know about or suspect any foul play in the past?</i></p>
<p>1928</p> <p>HC Deb 21 March 1928 vol 215 cc465-525, Safeguarding of industry, Captain Streatfeild</p> <p>I would like to touch shortly on the granite industry [...] We have to deal with granite curbs and setts and monumental stone, in regards to which the trade has been almost entirely taken by Scandinavia. I want to urge upon the hon. Gentleman that if any help is sought to be given to the granite industry by the imposition of duty on imported monumental stone, the help will be very little. I would urge that, if the monumental granite industry is to be helped, marble must come under the duty as well.</p>	<p><i>Movements in the marble industry, but how must this information be judged?</i></p>

A6.2 Archival sources related to marble and marble working

<p>1932</p> <p>Sale, 1932</p>	<p><i>The NEC sold Marble Island along with its other possessions to the Norwegian Government. At a huge loss.</i></p>
<p>Polar Record 1931-1940</p> <p>The journal reports on the annual Norwegian fisheries expeditions to Spitsbergen between 1930 and 1939. Ny Ålesund in Kongsfjorden was used as a base. No mention of Marble Island.</p>	<p><i>It is possible that the small fisheries outpost on Marble Island was used following the sale of the claim to the Norwegians, but this has not been looked into in any detail.</i></p> <p><i>The fisheries activities will have added to the overall environmental impact as well as the archaeological site formation processes.</i></p>
<p>1960</p> <p>Siggerud, T. 1960. The iron occurrence at Farmhamna, Vestspitsbergen. <i>Årbok 1960</i>, p. 89.</p>	<p>He gathered evidence from the old workings and made additional observations before tackling the customary idea that the action of permafrost caused the marbles to fall apart when they were transported to a warmer climate. Laboratory tests confirmed his hypothesis that thawing could not be to blame, thus he pinpointed tectonic disturbances at depth to be the cause for the unconsolidated state of the marbles.</p>
<p>1968</p> <p>13 boreholes listed in the calendar on site, several boreholes located in the field</p>	<p><i>A search of the Yearbooks of the Norwegian Polar Institute, which lists the NPI expeditions and publications in this and subsequent years as well as those of 'others' has not revealed the nature of the drillers nor any record of the boreholes.</i></p> <p><i>A search of several NPI Skrifter has not lead to anything yet either. 13 substantial boreholes and no sign of them! Surely a record must be somewhere...</i></p> <p><i>The borehole logs would provide crucial data about the marble.</i></p>
<p>Ongoing</p> <p>Hunting and tourism</p>	<p><i>The influence of past, present, and future hunting and tourism must not be overlooked in the site formation processes.</i></p> <p><i>Visitors will commonly have a a negative, i.e. destructive, effect on the material remains. They may have introduced structures and objects of no archaeological value.</i></p> <p><i>Visitors will have had an impact on the local environment, not only by decimating animal populations but also by introducing species, i.e. grasses.</i></p>

A6.3 Home Office statistics, 1902-12

	1902	1903	1904	1905	1906	1907	1908	1909	1910	1911	1912	
	Qty (t)											
Algeria	375	700	530	451	460	355	440	450	600	480	448	
Argentine Rep.								2	4200	300	5900	230112
Belgium	15490	16735	17740	17254	15335	16190	15835	14632	15762	15120	17015	
Canada								n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	
France	118894	136615	118654	115222	119488	121425	113743	80313	78507	207109	173285	
Greece							12624	11448	11148	7404	6867	2860
India						1585	2612	2720	1995	2234	1887	2340
Mexico	1030	1462	964	742	618	897	1283	1289	1103	903	1774	
Quebec								n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	

A6.4 Iona Marble Co., Ltd: summary of company file

National Archives of Scotland
The Iona Marble Company, Limited
BT2/6164

April, 10, 1906	Application for a Certificate of Incorporation 7 original subscribers, a granite merchant, a married lady, a solicitor, a ? consultant, a law clerk, an accountant Edward de Patoul, 50 Wellington St, Glasgow the granite merchant and driver Witness to the signatures a typist All from Glasgow
April 10, 1906	Memorandum and Articles of Association Capital is £2,000 divided into 1,250 preference shares and 750 ordinary shares of £1 each 7 founders' shares
April 12, 1906	Declaration of Compliance
April 12, 1906	The Nominal Capital As above
April 14, 1906	Certificate of Incorporation Under the Companies Acts 1862 and 1900
May 9, 1906	Minute of Agreement between The Iona Marble Company, Limited, Edward de Patoul and William Fulton
May 9, 1906 – May 14, 1906	Return of Allotments 529 preference shares 50 ordinary 'assignment to Company of Lease of Marble Quarries in Iona and rights thereunder and also contracts already made for sale of Iona marble [...] Only 10 preference shareholders, mostly directors to 100 each All 750 ordinary shares subscribed to by De Patoul
May 30, 1906	Notice of the Situation of the Registered Office 146 West Regent Street, Glasgow
May 30, 1906	Copy of the Register of Directors or Managers Edward de Patoul, now marble merchant William R. Aitken, a builder Malcolm Campbell, a florist Mungo M. Graham, an accountant Signed by the secretary W. Fairley Smith

A6.4 Iona Marble Co., Ltd: summary of company file

June 18, 1906	Summary of Capital and Shares As above
[October 4, 1906]	Report [...] of the Iona Marble Co. Ltd Preliminary expenses: Registration agents 16/10/0 Printers' account 3/9/6 Seal, Registers 3/7/6 Law Expenses 30/0/0 53/7/0
March 21, 1907	Return of Allotments 50 shares allotted to Thomas Lamb, Glasgow, quarry manager
May 22, 1907	Return of Allotments 350 preference shares allotted Claud Allen, ship owner, 200 Malcolm Campbell, director, 50 Mungo Graham, director, 50 William Fairley Smith, 50
December 31, 1907	Summary of Capital and Shares 929 preference shares and 750 ordinary shares allotted 16 shareholders De Patoul transferred 100 pref shares to Norman McLoed on October 10, 1907; 250 ordinary shares each to Andrew Laird, W. Fairley Smith, and Claud Allan [a scam?!]
February 17, 1908	Summary of Capital and Shares As above [no change at all, besides there being 18 shareholders after some transfers] De Patoul not a director, Laird and Allan on the board
March 31, 1908	Copy of Register of Directors or Managers Campbell, Graham, Aitken, Allan, Laird De Patoul listed as resigned
May 22, 1908	Return of Allotments 200 preference shares 100 to John Faill, a contractor 100 to Edward Watson, a butcher
August 5, 1908	Return of Allotments 100 preference shares to Roderick Geddes Brown, Edinburgh, solicitor
May 18, 1909	Petition [...] for Winding Up of the Iona Marble Company, Limited

A6.4 Iona Marble Co., Ltd: summary of company file

- January 10, 1914 Letter from H. M. D. Watson, liquidator, to the Registrar of Joint Stock Companies
Consent to the Hebridean Marble Company using the name "Iona Marbles Limited"
- December 15, 1936 Letter from Registrar of Companies to Iona Marble Company, Limited
To enquire if affairs are fully wound up
- December 22, 1936 Letter from Lindsey Howe to the Registrar of Companies
Acted as agents in the liquidation in 1909, no formal dissolution order was granted, on June 9, 1910, the Court approved of auditor's report on the accounts and authorised liquidation, the Company had no assets, the Company has not carried on business since
- January 8, 1937 Edinburgh Gazette, p. 26
Iona marble Company, Ltd struck off the register
- April 9, 1937 company dissolved according to Companies Act, 1929
Last note on file by Registrar of Companies

A6.5 Skye Marble Ltd: summary of company file

National Records of Scotland
Skye Marble Limited
BT2/6606

- August 16, 1907 Certificate of Incorporation
Companies Act, 1862 and 1900
- August 16, 1907 Declaration of Compliance
- August 16, 1907 Memorandum and Articles of Association
7 original subscribers, one share each
Four granite and/or marble merchants, two writers of the signet, a builder
- August 16, 1907 Notice of Nominal Capital
£20,000 divided into 20,000 of £1 each
Walter W. Gunn, managing director
- August 16, 1907 Notice of Situation of Registered Offices
2 Thistle Court, Edinburgh
- August 16, 1907 List of directors
Daniel Dunkin Fenning, London, granite and marble merchant
Fred W. Fenning, London, granite and marble merchant
Walter William Gunn, Edinburgh, marble merchant
- August 16, 1907 Return of Allotments
3,027 shares allotted in cash
8,000 shares allotted for other than cash [lease of the quarries]
14 shareholders, 7 of these are founders at 1 share each, Gunn holds the 8,000 'other' shares, Fenning & Co (London) holds 2,000, Meikle (500), Nisbet (250), Dickson (250), Finlayson (20), and Milne (50)
- September 28, 1907 Consent to act as Directors
Adam Longmore, Edinburgh, marble merchant
Richard Leighton, London, marble merchant
William Meikle, Edinburgh, planter
- September 30, 1907 Prospectus
Skye Marble, Limited; capital £20,000, £8,000 issued and fully paid up in payment of the purchase of the Lease of Skye marble; 12,000 now offered for subscription (3,027 already applied for and allotted), 5s per share to be paid on application, 5s on allotment; listing directors, managing director, solicitor, bankers, auditor, secretary (William R. Milne), and registered office; lease of marble in the Isle of Skye between Lord Macdonald and W. W. Gunn for 50 years (!) from March

31, 1906; rent £100 per annum; marble blocks, slabs, and chips; report by Ben. N. Peach (formerly Geological Survey) very favourable; trial quarry operations between March and December 1906: 13,000 tons extracted; demand enormous, business very large; Italian figures: close to 100,000 tons imported into 'this country'; Skye has geographical advantages; [photos taken]

- November 18, 1907 Certificate [...] to commence business
- February 1, 1908 Return of Allotments
1,396 ordinary shares allotted, of which 1,000 to Devillas & Co., Ltd (France), a marble merchant
- February 6, 1908 Notice of statutory meeting to be held on February 15
12,423 shares allotted, 8,000 of which as said; total amount of cash received £2,175 5s and £500 paid in advance of calls; costs: plant and machinery 166:15:5, quarry developments or preliminary expenses incl wages 208:4:7, implements 2;11:0, rent 50:0:0, salaries 75:0:0, freight, pier dues & insurance 12:2:6, preliminary expenses of the company: 140:0:0; same directors; same secretary
- February 29, 1908 Summary of Capital and Shares
12,423 shares allotted, 4,423 fully paid up in cash, directors and secretary as above
- December 18, 1908 – Return of Allotment
December 23, 1908 3,625 shares allotted, 2000 to an Edinburgh coal master, also Meikle (250) and F. W. Fenning (50)
- January 29, 1909 Balance Sheet made up to December 31, 1908 (see March 18, 1909: summary of share capital and shares)
- March 5, 1909 Notice of Change in the Situation of the registered Offices
11 Albyn Place, Edinburgh
- March 18, 1909 Summary of Share Capital and Shares
15,348 shares issued, 7,348 fully paid up in cash, 8,000 in other than cash; no debt due from company in respect of all mortgages and charges
Balance sheet made up to December 31, 1908 [photographed]
Gunn holds 2,600 shares of the original 8,000; he transferred 324 (08/10/08), 1100 (11/09/08), 50 (09/10/08), 100 (03/11/08), 250 (14/12/08), 10 (17/12/08), 15 (17/09/08) to 'persons who are still members'
Longmore holds 78; he transferred 734 on 17/09/08
Directors: D. D. Fenning gone, John D. Brunton (Musselburgh) and James McKelvie (Edinburgh) joined

A6.5 Skye Marble Ltd: summary of company file

March 25, 1909	Return of Allotments 850 shares issued, mainly Meikle family
April 2, 1909	Special Resolution (confirmed) A section in the Company's articles was deleted
August 30, 1909 – September 18, 1909	Return of Allotments 100 shares allotted
September 14, 1909	Special Resolution (confirmed) Capital to be increased by £20,000 to £40,000
December 31, 1909	Balance sheet made up to this date [photographed]
January 6, 1910	Returns 100 shares
June 21, 1910 – July 13, 1910	Return of Allotments 3,302 ordinary shares allotted
October 17, 1910 – November 15, 1910	Returns 300 shares
	Directors: Gunn (?!), Longmore, Walter Ralph Herring for Richard Leighton, Meikle, Brunton, McKelvie, F. W. Fenning resigned
1910	[some efforts to get the Memorandum of association altered; to what avail?!!]
1910	[also some improper dealing of 750 shares that was apparently sorted out]
February 23, 1911 – March 23, 1911	Returns 9,474 shares, of which McKelvie took 5,000, other directors also took some
April 7, 1911	Returns 3,845 ordinary shares Again taken by directors, Meikle with 1,130, McKelvie with 1,000
May 25, 1911	Returns 650 ordinary shares, some to Meikle family
August 23, 1911	Notice of Change in the Situation of Registered Office Now at Broadford on the isle of Skye
August 31, 1911	Special Resolution Capital to be increased from £40,000 to £60,000

- September 14, 1911 Summary of Share Capital and Shares
32,824 shares taken up, 24,824 paid wholly in cash, 8,000 other
Including Balance Sheet made up to December 31, 1910
[photographed]
Directors: McKelvie, Meikle, Herring, Longmore, John Dempster (in
place of Brunton, resigned)
Devillers of France transferred their shares and ceased to be members
- December 31, 1911 Balance Sheet [photographed]
- January 4, 1912 Returns
1,000 shares to Meikle
- February 14, 1912 Returns
7,000 ordinary shares to Dempster
- June 13, 1911 Returns
1,500 ordinary shares to Meikle and Glassford (1,000, a retired planter)
- July 22, 1912 Summary of Share Capital and Shares
42,324 shares issued, 34,324 for cash, 8,000 other
- November 21, 1912 Extraordinary Resolution (passed)
'That it has been proven to the satisfaction of this Meeting that the
Company cannot by reason of its liabilities continue its business, and
that it is advisable to wind up the same, and accordingly, that the
Company be wound up voluntarily.'
- March 12, 1915 Letter from Lord Cullen
Approves liquidator's final account, dissolves company from date
hereof

A6.6 Summary of environmental impact and disease, 1912/13

Summarised from the Day Book kept by David Booth, September 1912 - July 1913

Note:

Leech (1920) reports that the wintering party consisting of a manager (Miller), a mechanic (Booth), the cook (Booth's brother), and eight men of unknown nationality. It is not known how many men arrived on the first ship in spring 1913.

	Date	Booth's comments
	Sep 19	ship left this afternoon
	Dec 13	men killed last pig
Jan	23	2 men to Cross Bay for provisions, have nothing but tinned boiled meat left wish we had open water so as to get some seal meat nearly run out of everything in food living on nothing but tinned boiled meat and that is also nearly finished very
Feb	2	little butter left men out in boats trying to get some seagulls for food as we are in a very bad way for all sorts of meat, they got twenty two gulls which we will have for lunch tomorrow
	15	wish we could get some seals or bears
	16	had seagulls for lunch they are not bad
	22	went to Cross Bay for provisions
Mar	8	took out boat today got 3 seals and some seagulls very little food left
	12	out in boat afternoon got 45 seagulls but no seals
	15	rest of men took out boat and got 4 seals trapper mentioned, I had to go for matches [to Cross Bay] as we had none in Kings Bay
	31	Bay
Apr	17	stranded for 3 days at Mitre Hook with nothing to eat but hard bread
	27	was out in boat today with brother got 3 very large seals in about half an hour got 20 birds today have only one day's butter left have heard from Cross Bay that ship is expected every day hope it won't be long
May	25	ship is expected every day hope it won't be long
	26	I got 40 birds today it is the only food them and seal meat that we have to rely on
	30	today ship came
Jun	5	fired eight shots with dynamite for the uprights of the storehouse
	6	fired twenty eight shots today Barrett sick today, complaining of severe pains in the stomach I think he has a slight touch of colic
	7	touch of colic
	14	Barrett ill
	16	Simpson in bed with sore heel slight blood poisoning Kutzberg reported sick today had to isolate him from other men put him in tent,
	17	Simpson in bed
	18	Barrett returned to work, Simpson and Kutzberg in bed
	19	Simpson and Kutzberg in bed
	20	2 of Smiths men building lavatory, Simpson and Kutzberg still ill
	21	Simpson still unable to work, landing cattle
	23	we have received 373 sacks of coal since coming to Marble Island in summer
	24	3 men sick now Young influenza Rogers same and Simpson sore heel

A6.6 Summary of environmental impact and disease, 1912/13

25 five men off with sickness. Rogers Fox. Brackley. And Simpson, also Thrift [there's more detail but this summary has been kept brief from this point onwards]

26 Thrift started to work this morning. Brackley 102 [Booth records temperatures from now on]. Rogers and Fox very ill have sent telegram for Doctor, Simpson still off

27 putting gravel around Camp Warburg and Camp Smith, all sick men a little better
28 sick men no better
29 sick men just the same
30 Rogers little better, others the same, doctorship handed to me by Gibson

Jul 1 putting gravel around storehouse, Brackley better, Rogers and Fox still ill, another patient Fryer chill no temperature, Simpson still unable
2 made path from shore to Camp Peirson, Rogers, Fox, Brackley, Fryer ill, Clinkerberry in bed with pain in the head
3 made path from shore to first camp, same men ill
4 Fryer and Clinkerberry started work
5 four men ill
6 trapper mentioned, four men ill
7 four men ill
8 four men ill

9 trappers came back today from Cross Bay, preserved potatoes, four men ill
Rogers and Fox the same, Simpson and Bradley started work, gave them light job of
10 cleaning boring machines
11 finished cleaning machines, put one in store, two men ill
12 Rogers taken away by Mansfield, left Fox
13 Fox not good
14 Fox not good
15 Fox better
16 Fox alright
17 Fox normal
18 Fox normal
20 Fox normal
21 Fox alright but weak
22 Fox better
23 [end of Day Book]

A6.6 Summary of environmental impact and disease, 1912/13

From Booth's photo album

The cook. Booth's brother?

One of the seals caught in 1912/13?

A6.6 Summary of environmental impact and disease, 1912/13

Probably the cook who arrived in spring 1913. And that's NOT a 'seagull'...

Appendix 7

Outreach in Svalbard

Frigga får oppfylt marmordrø

Frigga Kruse tror ikke på den gjengse teorien om marmorfadesen i Ny-London.

» Christian Nicolai Bjørke

■ I forrige uke var styret i Svalbard Miljøvernfond samlet i Longyearbyen for å dele ut 5,3 millioner kroner. Alle tilreisende til Svalbard betaler 150 kroner i miljøgebyr gjennom sin flybillett eller cruisereise. Pengene går inn i et fond, og to ganger i året deles pengene ut.

Blant de heldige mottakerne er Frigga Kruse, en uavhengige tysk forsker som har fått 88.000 kroner for å se nærmere på det gamle marmorbruddet Ny-London i Kongsfjorden.

– Jeg kaller det ikke lenger Ny-London. Hvis du ser på historien til den britiske gruvedriften på Svalbard, ser du at de aldri brukte det navnet, men kalte det for Marble Island, sier hun.

Frostspregning

Kruse tok nylig en doktorgrad på britisk gruvedrift i arktiske strøk, og så spesielt på selskapet Northern Explorations forsøk på å dra i gang uttak av marmor på

Blomsterhalvøya i Kongsfjorden i 1911. Det ble bygget en imponerende infrastruktur, men driften ble oppgitt i 1920. Det er en allmenn oppfatning av at skjedde på grunn av frostsprengning i marmorstykkene. Det er ikke Kruse like sikker på at er sant.

– Jeg har konsultert gamle kilder uten å finne svaret. Når jeg sjekker blogger eller hører hva guider på cruiseskip forteller, sier de at permafrosten falt sammen når den kom til varmere strøk. Jeg håper å finne svaret, sier hun.

Norsk forsker

Kruse skal følge i fotsporene til den norske forskeren Thor Siggerud. Han skrev i 1960 en artikkel der han lanserte en teori om at marmorproblemene kom som følge av et større strukturelt problem med forekomstene på Blomsterhalvøya.

Arbeidet kommer til å bli todelt. Først skal hun konsultere arkiver for å finne ut mer om marmormarkedet på 1910-tallet. Deretter blir det feltarbeid på Blomsterhalvøya sommeren 2014.

GEOLOG: Frigga Kruse i felt på Blomsterhalvøya. FOTO: PRIVAT

... men Frigg fikk mest penger

Aeco, med daglig leder Frigg Jørgensen i spissen, fikk det største beløpet fra Svalbard Miljøvernfond.

» Christian Nicolai Bjørke

■ Desidert mest penger gikk til Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (Aeco). De har fått 650.000 kroner for å lage en animasjonfilm av sine retningslinjer for besøkende på Svalbard. Siden 2007 har organisjonen laget såkalte «guidelines» som gir cruiseturister råd om hvordan man skal ferdes miljøvennlig, sikkert og uten å ødelegge kulturminner.

Aeco-direktør Frigg Jørgensen er svært glad for å ha mottatt midler.

– Nå skal vi ta kontakt med de produksjonselskapene vi snakket med før vi lagde søknaden, og vurdere hvem vi skal samarbeide med, sier Jørgensen.

Klar til sesongen

Animasjonsfilmen skal produseres på flere ulike språk og skal vises om bord i de rundt 25 skipene som er tilknyttet Aeco. I overkant av 11.000 turister reiser hvert år med disse.

– Jeg håper at filmen blir ferdig til mai 2014, når sesongen begynner, sier hun.

17 prosjekter delte på høstens pengepott, og styret roser årets søknader.

– Vi ser at søkerne har blitt flinkere til å konkretisere søknadene, sier styremedlem Aud Andersen.

De overordnede retningslin-

jene fra Miljøverndepartementet er at klima skal settes høyt på dagsordenen i år.

– Spesielt formidlingsprosjekter til allmennheten ses på som et viktig middel, sier styreleder Ann-Kristin Olsen.

Klima høyest

De fleste prosjektene som har fått støtte, kan gå inn under et utvidet klimabegrep.

– Men det er ikke slik at vi løfter fram dårlige søknader for å fylle en klimavote, sier styremedlem Stefan Norris.

15 søkere fikk ikke gjennomslag for sin søknad. Styreleder Olsen sier at de vil få en redegjørelse i posten.

– Alle er også velkommen til å ta kontakt hvis de vil ha en mer inngående begrunnelse, sier Olsen.

Ber russerne søke

■ Ingen av høstens søknader handler om å ruste opp noen av kulturminnene på Svalbard. Det håper nyvalgt styremedlem Siri Hoem å gjøre noe med. Hun har tidligere vært kulturminnerådgiver for Sysselmannen i tre år, og sier at en justering i fondets retningslinjer gjør at det nå er mulig å søke om støtte til restaurering av kulturminner fra etter 1946.

– Det åpner opp for mange bygg i Barentsburg og Pyramiden. Dessuten er det stort potensiale i Longyearbyen, som for eksempel en del brakker i Nybyen og private hytter i området, sier Hoem.

– I løpet av 10-20 år kan mange av disse kulturminnene jeg tenker på gå tapt,

rømmen

Disse får penger

Norsk Polarinstitutt

Plast i havhest
400 000 kroner

UMB

GPS-overvåkning av rein
283 000 kroner

Nina

Klima, isbjørn og fugl
279 150 kroner

Aeco

AECO's guidelines as animation film
650 000 kroner

Store Norske

Forprosjekt for energisparetiltak i Svea
100 000 kroner

Unis

AtmoPart
250 000 kroner

Norsk institutt for luftforskning

Måling av luftforurensing i Ny-Ålesund
500 000 kroner

Svalbard Reiseliv AS

Merkeordningen «Bærekraftig reisemål»
350 000 kroner

Akvaplan-niva

Metoder for miljøklassifisering
290 000 kroner

Longyearbyen lokalstyre Bedrift KF

Søppelamnesti del 2
250 000 kroner

Frigga Kruse

«Marble at fault»
88 000 kroner

Longyearbyen hundeklubb

Isolering av klubbhus
34 000 kroner

Svalbard Turn

Orienteringskart
18 000 kroner

Norsk Polarinstitutt

Svalbardreinen
498 000 kroner

Ecofact Nord AS

Svalbardflora.net
480 000 kroner

Snøball Film AS

Konsekvenser av klimaendringene
400 000 kroner

NTNU

Varmere, våtere, villere Svalbard
430 100 kroner

sier hun.

Miljøvernfondets sekretær Asbjørn Hagen var nylig i Barentsburg for å informere om mulighetene for å søke fondet. I løpet av fondets seks år lange historie har det aldri skjedd at en russisk søknad har blitt tildelt penger.

– Gjennom tidene har det komme én eller to stykker. Men disse har ikke vært gode nok, sier styremedlem Ottar Krohn.

Amnesti for skutere

■ Longyearbyen lokalstyre (LL) har fått 250.000 kroner til et nytt søppelamnesti. Fjorårets søppelamnesti førte til at folk kunne kaste avfall gratis så lenge midlene rakk. I årets søknad sier LL at det i første rekke skal handle om gamle, utrangerte skutere.

FOTO: CHRISTIAN NICOLAI BJØRKE

Skifter ut halve styret

■ Tre av styremedlemmene i Svalbard Miljøvernfond hadde sitt siste møte forrige uke. De tre til venstre i bildet, Ottar Krohn (fylkesmiljøvern sjef i Østfold og tidligere miljøvern sjef hos Syssele mannen på Svalbard),

Ann-Kristin Olsen (fylkesmann i Vest-Agder og tidligere syssele mann på Svalbard) og Aud Andersen (nestleder i Svalbard Reiselivsråd) går ut av styret. De som fortsetter i styret fram til 2017 er Stefan Norris (WWF,

t.h.), Siri Hoem (Forsvarsbygg, grønn genser) og Anne-Line Pedersen (Longyearbyen lokalstyre, ikke til stede da bildet ble tatt). Asbjørn Hagen (nummer to fra høyre) er sekretær i Svalbard Miljøvernfond.

UPCOMING PUBLIC WORKSHOP!

FROM BOOM

TO RUST

New archaeological insights into the British industrial past on Svalbard

Dr. Frigga Kruse (Arctic Centre, Groningen, NL) presents the results of her PhD research on British mining between 1904 and 1953.

Her new project "Marble at Fault" is sponsored by the Svalbard Environmental Protection Fund. It aims to explain the abandoned marble quarries of the Northern Exploration Co. in Kongsfjord.

After the presentation, Frigga invites experts and the public to engage in a group discussion.

Place: Lassegrotta, Forskningsparken
Date: Saturday, 25. January 2014
Time: to be confirmed
Free admittance

For more details, please contact
f.kruse@rug.nl

Marmoren kan ha skylden

Frigga Kruse og Benjamin Koster tror kvaliteten på marmoren på Blomstrandhalvøya kan være en årsak til at driften ble nedlagt for åtti år siden. Men det kan også være andre årsaker.

» Christopher Engås

■ Frigga Kruse fra universitetet i Groningen i Nederland fikk i vår støtte fra Svalbards miljøvernfond for å forske på marmorutvinningen på Blomstrandhalvøya fra 1910 til 1932. Driften foregikk i perioder, og selskapet som sto bak var det engelske selskapet Northern Exploration Co.

– Målet vårt er å komme fram til en sannsynlig årsak til at drifta ble innstilt. Var det kvaliteten på marmoren, konjunktorene – eller rett og slett inkompetanse, sier Frigga Kruse.

Radarteknologi

I begynnelsen av juli var hun på Blomstrandhalvøya sammen med geolog Benjamin Koster fra universitetet i Aachen i Tyskland. Koster har saumfart stedene det ble drevet marmorutvinning med en såkalt GPA (ground penetrating radar) for å undersøke kvaliteten på forekomstene. Koster er for tiden i Tyskland hvor han jobber med å analysere resultatene.

– Det som er interessant er om forekomsten er full av sprekker

HVA SKJEDDE?: Benjamin Koster jobber med å undersøke grunnen ved bruddet fra 1912. I bakgrunnen ses driftsbygningen og deler av maskineriet som ble brukt da Northern Exploration Co. drev marmorutvinningen.

FOTO: FRIGGA KRUSE

som gjør at den viste seg ikke drivverdig. Hvis det er slik at hevingen av landet har ført til mange sprekker, blir marmoren ubrukkelig. Det vi har observert er at det finnes åpenbare sprekker både i dagen, og lenger ned, men analysen vil vise hvordan kvaliteten er, sier Kruse.

Sammensatt årsak

Marmorforekomsten i området er av en mørk grå type, ganske ulik den hvite typen kjent fra sør-Europa. Dagbruddene er

tydelig i terrenget i dag, og det står også bygninger igjen fra gruve drifta den gang.

Frigga Kruse vil ikke kalle drifta for en fiasko. Hun mener det kan være en sammensatt årsak til at marmorutvinninga tok slutt.

– Vi skal analysere resultatene først, men allerede nå er det klart at dette ikke er sort-hvitt. Det er tydelig at et av dagbruddene, som ble brutt om vinteren, er på et sted hvor det er åpenbare sprekker, også i overflaten, slik at

det aldri skulle vært startet drift der. Det åpner for muligheten om at inkompetanse kan ha vært medvirkende. Prisene på verdensmarkedet er en annen faktor. Etter første verdenskrig gikk Europa sakte men sikkert inn i en depresjon, slik at etterspørselen etter luksusmaterialer som marmor falt, sier hun.

– Uansett er dette spor etter den første industrialiseringen på Svalbard, og omstendighetene rundt den bør studeres, legger Frigga Kruse til.

LANGT NORD: Blomstrandhalvøya ligger rett nord for Ny-Ålesund i Kongsfjorden.

KART: NORSK POLARINSTITUTT

FELTARBEID: Frigga Kruse og Benjamin Koster analyserer nå resultatene etter undersøkelsene.

FOTO: CHRISTOPHER ENGÅS

Marble at Fault

Why did the Northern Exploration Co. abandon its marble quarries on Blomstrand?

Since the glacier Blomstrandbreen has retreated in recent years, we now know Blomstrandhalvøya in Kongsfjorden to be an island (Fig. 1). Its history is colourful and it is very popular with tourists. In 1906, the English explorer Ernest Mansfield found it to be made entirely of marble. On his advice, the Northern Exploration Co. started operations here in 1911 (Fig. 2). After a voluntary absence during the First World War, the NEC renewed quarrying in 1919 (Fig. 3) only to abandon the site in 1920. The marble has not been worked since. What led to this abandonment?

The project title 'Marble at Fault' is a play on words, suggesting that geological faulting, i.e. structural weaknesses in the make-up of the island, could be to blame. Fractures in the rock might have caused the quarried blocks to break apart, thereby making them worthless (Fig. 4). In order to shed light on this, I asked the German geologist Benjamin Koster to carry out a ground-penetrating radar (GPR) survey at an archaeological scale (Fig. 5). Targeting the subsurface, the GPR survey might reveal faults but also areas of solid rock not visible from the surface. We wanted to know if further working at the existing quarries would have produced waste rock or sound marble (Fig. 6). We also wanted to know whether several historical boreholes were drilled into outcrops of economic potential. Following the survey, we found that there were disturbances in the marble at every survey location. Yet, there were also intact areas with economic potential. The next step, therefore, is to ask a marble expert at what percentage of waste rock a quarry becomes non-profitable.

In addition to the GPR survey, I undertook archival research in the UK (Fig. 7). I hoped to find information about historical marble markets and demand, but this was not an easy task. It appears that there was a growing demand before the First World War, which I can trace in the sources. However, after the war, the construction industry addressed the housing needs of returning soldiers, and marble being impractical for the purpose, the demand for it decreased markedly.

'Marble at Fault' thus exposed some problems with the High Arctic marble, which may have undermined its workability and profitability. Yet, even if the quality had been excellent and operations had been easy, the global market at the time was such that Blomstrand marble would in all likelihood not have found a buyer – despite Svalbard being closer to London than Greece.

This project could only be carried out with the kind support of the Svalbard Environmental Protection Fund and with the assistance of the University of Groningen.

Frigga Kruse

Arctic Centre, University of Groningen

Figures

Fig. 1 Map of Blomstrand

Fig. 2 Settlement on Blomstrand under construction

Fig. 3 Shallow quarry opened in 1919

Fig. 4 Fracturing is an ongoing process, probably because the weight of glaciers has been lifted off Blomstrand in recent times

Fig. 5 GPR survey in progress

Fig. 6 Does the area next to an existing quarry have economic potential?

Fig. 7 Archival research in the impressive library of the North of England Institute of Mining and Mechanical Engineers (NEIMME) in Newcastle-upon-Tyne, UK

Was the rock around the old quarries and boreholes disturbed or did it have economic potential?

What other reasons may have led to the abandonment? Archival research might provide an answer.

Some disturbances were clearly visible at the surface. The GPR survey revealed areas of disturbances but also intact rock. How much waste rock is too much waste rock?

Irregardless of the quality of High Arctic marble and the ease of working it, the documents indicate that global markets and a lack of demand may yet be to blame.

